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MODEL ORDER REDUCTION TECHNIQUES FOR MARINE SHOCK ISOLATION SEATS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction

High speed Planing craft (HSPC) are marine vessels designed to elevate and glide on the top of the water surface at high speeds. Consequently, HSPCs experience complex vibrational phenomena that stem from an interplay of hydrodynamic pressure loads that are generally a function of the relative velocity between hull and the water surrounding it, the dynamics of the propulsion systems and inherent structural properties of the boat subsystems [1].

Shocks in HSPCs may result from varying sea states and operational conditions but they are primarily caused by abrupt hydrodynamic impacts which occur when the hull recontacts the water surface after becoming momentarily airborne during high-speed transits over wave crests [2]. These shocks far exceed the permitted levels for the human body [3]. The effects of these whole-body vibrations are strongly influenced by magnitude, waveform, and duration of exposure and prolonged exposure to these repeated shocks significantly impacts crew health and performance [4]. Considerable research has been directed at mitigating these vibrations using suspension seats as it is imperative for crew health and safety. This work focuses on a HSPC seat designed for such shock reduction.

Model Description

The system features a spring-damper suspension system linking the base plate and lower body to the upper body, seat frame, and cushion. The system functions like a parallelogram four-bar linkage mechanism with links that connect and constrain the upper body and seat frame relative to the lower body and base plate. A preliminary multibody model of the boat seat was developed using ADAMS View (Hexagon AB, Stockholm, SE) using nominal dimensions of an actual seat (Fig. 1). To simplify the digital model, the spring forces were applied directly instead of explicitly modelling the spring and damper elements. The links are modelled as flexible elements which were included in the model through a Component Mode Synthesis (CMS) approach. The model takes the accelerations of the base plate in the

X, Y, and Z directions as inputs and produces the seat accelerations in same directions as outputs.

A first validation of the model has been achieved using data from sea trials. Although lateral acceleration plays a key role in overall vibrational response [2], recorded data showed higher magnitudes of acceleration in the vertical direction, as expected. The computational cost of the preliminary multibody model is quite large. In the context of digital twins, high-fidelity real time simulations are essential [5], reiterating the need for the creation of a reduced order model of the boat seat that can deliver accurate simulation outputs with shorter computational times.

Figure 1. Multibody model of the HSPC shock isolation seat

Methodology

A range of different Model order reduction (MOR) methods have been explored for multibody systems [6] that can be broadly categorized into three classes.

Physics-based approaches include projection-based methods (e.g., Galerkin, Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD)) [7] and control-theoretic techniques (e.g., Balanced Truncation, Moment Matching using Krylov subspaces) [8] that reduce system dynamics through low-dimensional subspaces or stability-preserving frameworks, while methods like Lyapunov-Schmidt and Center Manifold allow for handling of nonlinearity.

Data-driven methods rely on simulation or experimental data, employing statistical tools or machine learning models such as Autoencoders and Neural ODEs. These methods are increasingly favoured for their ability to capture strong nonlinearities and scale with data [9].

Hybrid approaches include strategies like Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) and Quadratic Approximation Manifolds which leverage physical insight with data-driven techniques. They are more efficient in capturing nonlinearities or complex parametric dependencies while respecting the fundamentals of stability, causality and energy

consumption [10].

This study adopts an Operator Inference (OpInf) with Projection modelling approach [11], that belongs to the category of hybrid approaches. High-fidelity simulations “snapshots” were first normalized to avoid biases due to any modal parameter and then used to compute a reduced Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) basis. The full system states were projected onto this reduced basis and reduced coordinates were defined. Solving a Least Squares objective, the reduced operators representing the key dynamics of the system were learned non-intrusively. Linear Matrix Inequality (LMI) constraints were enforced to the reduced operators to preserve their structural integrity, like previous approaches [11,12]. This step ensured the stability of the deduced operators. Finally, a Newmark-Beta scheme was used to integrate the second order dynamics.

Results and future work

The accuracy of the multibody model is critically important as the simulation outputs serve as the foundational data for deriving the operators of the ROM. The model simulation results showed strong fidelity to the actual system in the vertical direction although high-frequency chatter was observed in the seat lateral acceleration. The damping parameters need further tuning for resolving this issue.

The hybrid non-intrusive ROM predicted vertical acceleration with a fair accuracy while significantly reducing computation time from 15 minutes in the full-order model to just 3 seconds for 60 seconds of output (Fig. 2). However, the presence of chatter in the simulation acceleration output in longitudinal and lateral directions also consequently led to the ROM outputs exhibiting chatter in the same directions. This issue could potentially be mitigated through the development of a more accurate multibody model.

Figure 2. Normalized vertical acceleration (Simulated) vs. ROM predicted.

Future work will focus on refining the multibody model to enhance simulation accuracy across the lateral and longitudinal axes, thereby minimizing bias in the ROM. Attention will also be directed to capture nonlinear effects to improve predictive accuracy and ensure more representative system dynamics.

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ANALISI DEI DIFETTI NEI CUSCINETTI VOLVENTI MEDIANTE TECNICHE VIBROACUSTICHE

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SOMMARIO

Introduzione

Negli ultimi anni, la manutenzione predittiva ha acquisito un ruolo strategico nell'industria, permettendo di anticipare i guasti, ridurre i tempi di inattività e migliorare l'efficienza operativa [1–2]. Tra le tecniche più consolidate per il monitoraggio delle macchine rotanti vi è l'analisi delle vibrazioni, basata principalmente sull'impiego di accelerometri [3]. Questa metodologia è ampiamente studiata, fornisce dati accurati e ripetibili, ed è largamente applicata nell'ambito industriale. Tuttavia, l'utilizzo degli accelerometri richiede il montaggio diretto sul macchinario, preferibilmente in prossimità del componente da monitorare. In alcune situazioni operative, questa esigenza può risultare problematica, soprattutto quando l'installazione è complessa o può interferire con la struttura della macchina. In alternativa, l'analisi acustica tramite microfoni presenta diversi vantaggi. Oltre a consentire il monitoraggio senza contatto, i microfoni, in particolare quelli a ultrasuoni, sono in grado di rilevare segnali a frequenze più elevate rispetto agli accelerometri tradizionali, ampliando le possibilità di individuazione precoce dei guasti [4-5].

In questo contesto, il presente lavoro esplora l'utilizzo combinato di microfoni e accelerometri per il monitoraggio delle condizioni dei cuscinetti volventi. Lo studio si concentra sull'analisi energetica del segnale acustico e sull'impiego di indicatori statistici semplici, evitando volutamente tecniche avanzate di elaborazione. L'obiettivo è valutare l'efficacia di un approccio pratico e a basso costo computazionale, validando una strategia ibrida basata su dati accelerometrici e microfonici.

Parametri utilizzati nell'analisi

Lo studio utilizza parametri statistici a bassa complessità per facilitare l'applicabilità industriale. Tra questi, la curtosi è fondamentale per individuare componenti impulsive nei segnali. Essa è definita come:

$$Kurtosis = E \left[\left(\frac{X-\mu}{\sigma} \right)^4 \right] = \frac{\mu_4}{\sigma^4} \quad (1)$$

Valori elevati di curtosi indicano distribuzioni leptocurtiche, tipiche di segnali con danni.

Altro parametro chiave presentato in questo lavoro è l'energia spettrale, calcolata come somma dei quadrati dei valori assoluti della FFT (Fast Fourier Transform) del segnale:

$$E(f) = \sum |X(f)|^2 \quad (2)$$

Per migliorare la risoluzione dell'analisi e l'interpretazione dei risultati, è stata utilizzata la suddivisione in bande di terzo d'ottava. Questo metodo è stato scelto perché offre un compromesso ottimale tra risoluzione in frequenza e gestibilità dei dati. Altri parametri calcolati, sono stati RMS, Crest Factor e Impulse factor.

Sistema di acquisizione e configurazione test

Sono state condotte acquisizioni su due banchi prova, variando sia il tipo di guasto che le condizioni operative del cuscinetto (Fig. 1).

Il primo banco prova (Fig. 1.a) consiste in un motore trifase con cuscinetti SKF 6205 testati in tre condizioni: sano, danneggiato da acido (anello esterno) e danneggiato da compressione, con rotazione a velocità costante di 1000 rpm.

Il secondo banco prova, AV TEST BENCH (Fig. 1.b), ha impiegato cuscinetti SKF YAR 204-2F a tre velocità (343,64 – 515,46 – 687,29 rpm), testati in due condizioni: sano e danneggiamento da saldatura (anello esterno).

Figure 1. Schema del sistema di misura utilizzato per il primo banco prova (a) e per il secondo banco prova (b).

Per garantire coerenza e confrontabilità, entrambi i test hanno utilizzato lo stesso sistema di acquisizione dati, composto da:

- Sistema DAQ ZoTech (48 kHz, 24 bit) per accelerometro e microfono standard, con comunicazione digitale per sincronizzazione precisa;
- Microfono a ultrasuoni Ultramic 384K WIND (384 kHz, 16 bit, con registratore integrato), posizionato a 15 cm dal cuscinetto in entrambi i test;
- Accelerometro monoassiale PCB Piezotronics 603M170, con banda fino a 14 kHz e sensibilità di 100 mV/g;
- Microfono omnidirezionale Brüel & Kjær 4189, risposta piatta 6 Hz–20 kHz, sensibilità 50 mV/Pa, posto a 45 cm nel primo test e a 15 cm nel secondo.

Per ottenere parametri statistici affidabili per il rilevamento di guasti, i segnali sono stati pre-elaborati filtrando ciascun canale nella sua banda utile. Ogni test ha previsto almeno 1 minuto di registrazione per condizione.

Sono state inoltre calcolate le frequenze caratteristiche di guasto (BPFO, BPFI, BSF, FTF) in base ai parametri geometrici e alla velocità dei cuscinetti (Tab. 1). Per validare la presenza di difetti indotti, è stata applicata l'analisi dell'involuppo di Hilbert ai segnali accelerometrici.

Tabella 1. Frequenze di danno del cuscinetto per una velocità di rotazione di 1000 e 343.64 rpm.

Parameters [Hz]	SKF 6205	SKF YAR204
Rotation Freq.	16.67	5.73
BPFO	59.75	20.53
BPFI	90.25	31.01
BFF	78.56	27.00
FTF	6.64	2.28

Risultati

Il primo banco di prova ha mostrato risultati promettenti, con differenze nette nei parametri statistici e nell'energia spettrale. In Fig. 4.a, la curtosi calcolata su bande di un terzo d'ottava evidenzia valori elevati per l'accelerometro nelle bande medio-alte (3,5–5 kHz e 6–12 kHz).

Anche i microfoni mostrano un aumento della curtosi alle alte frequenze (8–16 kHz), sebbene con differenze meno marcate rispetto all'accelerometro. È significativo che il microfono, pur distante dal cuscinetto, riesca comunque a rilevare variazioni.

Figure 2. Valori di Kurtosis (a) e Spectral Energy Ratio (b) per i tre sensori, calcolati in bande di terzi d'ottava.

Il microfono ad ultrasuoni si è rivelato molto sensibile, distinguendo chiaramente i guasti: quelli all'anello esterno (in rosso) tra 20–31,5 kHz, e quelli da compressione (in ocra) tra 20–63 kHz, con picco a 40 kHz.

Nel secondo banco di prova (Fig. 5.a), i parametri statistici calcolati sull'intero spettro segnalano che accelerometro e microfono a ultrasuoni distinguono chiaramente tra stati "sano" e "danneggiato", indipendentemente dalla velocità. Impulse factor e curtosi si confermano gli indicatori più sensibili. Il microfono standard mostra invece variazioni minime, ma fornisce informazioni utili se l'analisi è limitata a bande di terzi d'ottava.

Per il rapporto di energia spettrale (Fig. 5.b), entrambi i microfoni mostrano un aumento con la velocità dell'albero: il microfono standard tra 6,3–16 kHz (picco a 8 kHz), e quello a ultrasuoni tra 20–25 kHz e 31,5–63 kHz. Tuttavia, la loro efficacia cala alle basse velocità,

più nettamente nel caso del microfono a ultrasuoni. L'accelerometro presenta rapporti energetici elevati e stabili, soprattutto tra 8–12,5 kHz.

Figure 5. (a) Indicatori statistici per i tre sensori alle diverse velocità calcolati sull'intero spettro. (b) Spectral Energy Ratio calcolato in bande di terzi d'ottava per differenti velocità.

Conclusion e lavori futuri

I microfoni si sono dimostrati efficaci nel rilevare guasti nei cuscinetti volventi in condizioni controllate, rappresentando un possibile supporto agli accelerometri. Lo studio ha analizzato due tecniche principali di elaborazione: indicatori statistici e rapporto energetico spettrale, entrambe con risultati promettenti. In particolare, il rapporto energetico ha mostrato elevate potenzialità per la manutenzione predittiva, offrendo prestazioni comparabili alla cortosi. L'integrazione di microfoni a ultrasuoni nei sistemi di analisi vibroacustica può potenziare il monitoraggio, oltre a vantaggi pratici in termini di installazione e manutenzione.

Il lavoro futuro prevede l'adozione di metodi diagnostici più avanzati, nonché un confronto più approfondito tra sensori in condizioni operative variabili, inclusi diverse velocità di rotazione e distanze di acquisizione. Infine, si prevede una simulazione in presenza di rumore ambientale reale per testare l'effettiva robustezza del sistema in scenari industriali concreti.

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Application of Machine Learning-Based Prognostic Models for RUL Prediction on Rolling Element Bearings

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ABSTRACT

Introduction

Remaining Useful Life (RUL) prediction is a fundamental challenge in prognostics and health management, with significant implications for predictive maintenance strategies. Accurate failure forecasting enables optimization of maintenance schedules, reduction of unexpected downtime, and extension of component lifespans.

RUL prediction methodologies can be broadly categorized into model-based, data-driven, and hybrid approaches. Model-based approaches rely on physical degradation models describing deterioration mathematically, often requiring domain-specific knowledge and simplifying assumptions that may not capture real-world complexity [1]. Data-driven approaches leverage machine learning algorithms to learn degradation patterns directly from historical data without explicitly modeling the underlying physics [2].

As industrial systems become increasingly instrumented with sensors, the potential for data-driven prognostic models grows, yet significant challenges remain in translating sensor data into accurate RUL predictions. Within the data-driven paradigm, a significant divide exists between methods treating degradation as continuous versus those incorporating discrete state changes. Traditional approaches often assume component degradation follows a relatively smooth trajectory toward failure, including statistical models like proportional hazards models [3], neural networks [4] and support vector machines [5] that map features directly to RUL without explicitly considering state transitions.

More recently, researchers have recognized that many mechanical systems pass through distinct degradation states with different characteristics and degradation rates rather than degrading uniformly. State-based approaches identify these transitions and incorporate them into prediction models. Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) have been widely used to capture these state transitions in a probabilistic framework [6].

State-based approaches can potentially capture the non-stationary nature of degradation processes. By identifying system transitions from normal operation to various degradation states, these methods can adapt their predictions to the current state, leading to more accurate RUL estimates. However, implementing state-based approaches introduces challenges including accurate state detection and integration of state information into prediction models.

This study describes methodology to assess state detection impact on Remaining Useful Life (RUL) prediction on rolling element bearings, using a public dataset from the University of Ferrara. The framework integrates Binary Segmentation for state detection with Random Forest regression for RUL estimation, assessed through Leave-One-Bearing-Out cross-

validation. The aim is to assess whether including state information improves RUL prediction and offer guidance for future research in this domain.

Methodology

The proposed work evaluates the effect of state detection on RUL prediction using a structured approach that combines data preprocessing, state detection, and regression. The analysis is performed on a run-to-failure bearing dataset, where the goal is to predict the normalized RUL of each bearing at every time step. First, missing data and inconsistent sampling are addressed to ensure a uniform dataset. Feature normalization is performed using robust statistics to reduce the influence of outliers and enable fair comparison across bearings. State detection is subsequently applied to identify significant changes in the degradation process, segmenting each bearing’s life into two distinct operational states: healthy and degraded. This approach allows the model to incorporate both temporal and state-based information for RUL prediction. Finally, a Random Forest regression model is trained and evaluated using a cross-validation scheme designed to reflect real-world deployment, ensuring that model performance is assessed on truly unseen bearings. The main steps are summarized as follows:

1. **Data Preprocessing:** The dataset is preprocessed to handle missing values and standardize the features. Bearings with different sampling frequencies were linearly interpolated to obtain a uniform time base. The first 250 data points of each bearing were used to compute the healthy scale, which was then used to normalize the data. For increased robustness to eventual outliers, the scale was computed using the median and the median absolute deviation (MAD).
2. **State Detection:** The state detection is performed using Binary Segmentation, a recursive change-point detection algorithm first proposed by Scott and Knott [7]. Binary Segmentation detects multiple change points by recursively partitioning the time series data. For each bearing, the cumulative sum of the normalized features is computed; the change point is detected at time t that maximizes the absolute difference between the variance values of the segments before and after t . The dataset is then augmented with the state information, in particular by adding two new features, t_1 and t_2 , which count the number of time steps in which the series has been in the first and second state, respectively.
3. **RUL Prediction:** The target variable is the normalized RUL:

$$RUL_{norm} = 1 - \frac{t}{t_{max}} \quad (1)$$

where t is the time step and t_{max} is the maximum time step of the bearing, namely its time of failure. The RUL is then predicted using a Random Forest model, which is trained on the normalized features and the normalized RUL. Random Forests are a widely used ensemble learning method that combines multiple decision trees to improve prediction accuracy and control overfitting [8]. In this work, 100 trees were used to train the models. The models are robustly evaluated using Leave-One-Bearing-Out cross-validation (LOBOCV), which ensures that the model is trained on data from all bearings except one, and then tested on the left-out bearing. This process is iterated for all bearings, and the evaluation metrics are averaged across all folds to get a robust estimate of the model performance on unseen data.

Figure 1. Predicted vs actual normalized RUL without state detection (a), and with state detection (b).

Results

The analysis was conducted on the publicly available run-to-failure bearing dataset from the University of Ferrara, comprising vibration measurements from six rolling-element bearings tested to failure [9]. Each acquired segment was post-processed to extract three condition indicators: RMS, harmonic sum of the ball pass frequency outer race (BPFO), and IGCS_GS [10]. Figure 1 shows predicted and actual normalized RUL for one LOBOCV iteration with test bearing E3. The model successfully captures the characteristic decreasing trend of normalized RUL throughout the bearing’s operational lifetime. Notably, incorporating state detection yields substantial improvements in prediction performance, resulting in significantly more stable and accurate RUL estimates, particularly during the degradation phase when normalized RUL approaches zero, a period of paramount importance for predictive maintenance applications. The state-aware model’s predictions exhibit distinctive piecewise linear behavior, closely resembling established degradation models in RUL prediction literature. This suggests the binary state detection algorithm effectively captures the fundamental transition from healthy to degraded operational modes. However, a notable limitation emerges as RUL overestimation immediately preceding detected state transitions, more pronounced in the state-enhanced model. This indicates the underlying degradation process may be more complex than simple binary classification can represent, suggesting multi-state frameworks incorporating intermediate degradation phases could capture RUL evolution with greater accuracy.

Discussion

The observed discrepancy between model predictions and actual RUL values during state transitions reveals important insights into bearing degradation mechanisms. While the binary state framework successfully captures primary operational regime changes, systematic overestimation patterns suggest degradation follows more nuanced progression than a simple two-state model can represent.

The piecewise linear behavior exhibited by the state-aware model, while beneficial for

prediction stability, may oversimplify continuous degradation processes. A multi-state model could provide more accurate RUL predictions throughout the component's lifecycle by recognizing intermediate degradation phases and their associated degradation rates.

Future research will focus on improving state detection methodology using more advanced techniques, such as hidden Markov models (HMMs) operating in online settings without binary segmentation limitations.

Automating the state detection process will enable real-time dataset augmentation with state information, exploiting this information to improve RUL prediction accuracy. This would enable truly predictive maintenance systems adapting to changing component conditions and providing increasingly accurate RUL estimates as more data becomes available.

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CURIOSITÀ (IN)UTILI DI MECCANICA DEI SOLIDI

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Keywords: *Tensioni dischi rotanti, tensioni tubi in pressione, impronta pallone pallavolo.*

SOMMARIO

Introduzione

L'aereo Mustang P-51, il caccia-bombardiere americano sviluppato da North American a ridosso della Seconda guerra mondiale, è reputato uno degli aerei a elica più versatili di tutti i tempi. Lo progettò l'ingegnere austriaco-tedesco-americano Edgar Schmued nel 1939. Il passaggio dal concetto al prototipo durò solo 4 mesi, coinvolse 60 persone che in 60 000 ore di lavoro generarono i 2800 disegni [1] necessari per costruire il primo esemplare, collaudato nel 1940. La produzione di serie cominciò nel 1941, portando al dispiegamento complessivo di oltre 15 mila velivoli. Il tutto senza calcolatori, senza CAD, CAE, FEM, CAM o altri strumenti automatici, oggi pervasivi ma allora inesistenti.

Viene spontaneo chiedersi come un'impresa tecnico-organizzativa di questa portata sia stata possibile senza l'ausilio dei moderni mezzi digitali di calcolo. La mia tesi è che quel risultato fu raggiunto grazie alla mancanza di quei mezzi e fu facilitato dalla familiarità che i progettisti avevano con principi fisici essenziali, racchiusi in formule analitiche semplici, espressive, agili e, pur inesatte, commisurate allo scopo tecnico del momento. Sono anche convinto che l'attuale uso dei sistemi digitali di simulazione sia spesso sproporzionato rispetto al bisogno e ostacoli la comprensione dei fenomeni base da parte di chi li impiega. Ritengo che l'odierna formazione di ingegneri e progettisti dovrebbe ancora includere metodi e formule approssimate, per rimpiazzare o, quanto meno, convalidare i modelli virtuali più evoluti, pericolosamente sganciati dalla percezione sensoriale di chi li usa.

La Costruzione di Macchine è il tipico terreno dove è possibile ancorare la verifica e il progetto dei componenti meccanici a formule semplificate ma sostanziali. Qui espongo come espressioni imprecise, se ben interpretate, permettono di calcolare alcuni componenti di macchina col semplice uso di carta e penna. Mi concentrerò su cinque temi, presentati sotto forma di curiosità, tratti dagli ambiti generali dei dischi rotanti e degli involucri in pressione. Più precisamente: a) disco rotante di grosso spessore con foro libero; b) disco rotante di grosso spessore forzato su albero; c) cilindro di grosso spessore con pressione interna; d) tubo sottile in pressione; e) urto su piano rigido di membrana sferica in pressione. Lascio al lettore giudicare se le formule presentate, semplici e imperfette, siano utili o inutili nella preparazione dei giovani ingegneri e nella professione di costruttore di macchine.

Disco rotante con foro libero

Nel caso ideale di anello sottile rotante con velocità angolare ω , la tensione cerchiante, σ_{CR} , si calcola facilmente [2] dall'equilibrio del settore infinitesimo evidenziato in Fig. 1a

Figura 1. Corpi rotanti di ingombro assiale costante: (a) anello sottile; (b) disco spesso.

$$\sigma_{cR} = \rho\omega^2 R^2 \quad (1)$$

Nel disco spesso (Fig. 1b), la tensione cerchiante massima al raggio interno, σ_{ca} , vale [2]

$$\sigma_{ca} = \sigma_{c(R=b)} \{0.25[3 + \nu + (1 - \nu)(a/b)^2]\} \quad (2)$$

dove ν è il coefficiente di Poisson e $\sigma_{c(R=b)} = \rho\omega^2 b^2$. Per i metalli ($\nu = 0.3$) il termine tra parentesi graffe nella (2) vale 0.825 per $a \rightarrow 0$ (disco di spessore infinito) e tende a 1 per $a \rightarrow b$ (anello sottile). Si può quindi assumere $\sigma_{ca} \approx \sigma_{c(R=b)} = \rho\omega^2 b^2$, con errore in eccesso, al più, del 21% rispetto al valore esatto (2). In sintesi, la tensione cerchiante massima al raggio interno a del disco rotante di forte spessore, può essere calcolata, con piccolo errore, usando l'equazione (1) per anello sottile di *raggio pari al raggio esterno* del disco reale.

Disco rotante forzato su albero

Nel disco spesso forzato su albero pieno con interferenza diametrale i (Fig. 2a), la tensione ideale secondo Tresca, σ_{Ta} , al raggio interno a del disco vale [3] (E = modulo elastico)

$$\sigma_{Ta0} = Ei/(2a) \quad (3)$$

Quando il sistema ruota alla velocità ω , il disco matura le tensioni (2), crescenti con la velocità. Al contempo, l'interferenza effettiva diminuisce per effetto della centrifugazione. La tensione ideale complessiva, $\sigma_{Ta\omega_F}$, varia poco fino alla velocità di scalettamento (perdita totale di interferenza), ω_F , dove assume il seguente valore massimo [3]

$$\sigma_{Ta\omega_F} = E \frac{i}{2a} \left\{ 1 + \frac{1 - \nu}{3 + \nu} \left(\frac{a}{b} \right)^2 \right\} = \sigma_{Ta0} \left\{ 1 + \frac{1 - \nu}{3 + \nu} \left(\frac{a}{b} \right)^2 \right\} \quad (4)$$

Per $\nu = 0.3$ e $a/b \leq 0.5$ (un rapporto di forma che copre tutti i normali proporzionamenti) il termine tra parentesi graffe nella (4) è minore di 1.05. In altri termini, la tensione massima di Tresca nel disco rotante forzato è quasi indipendente dalla velocità e coincide, a meno del 5%, col valore di solo forzamento dato dalla (3).

Figura 2. Disco spesso forzato su albero: (a) solo forzamento; (b) forzamento e rotazione.

Cilindro di grosso spessore con pressione interna

La tensione cerchiante, σ_{cR} , nel cilindro sottile in pressione interna (Fig. 3a), vale [4]

$$\sigma_c = pR/s \quad (5)$$

La tensione cerchiante massima, σ_{ca} , al raggio interno del cilindro spesso (Fig. 3b), vale [4]

$$\sigma_{ca} = p \frac{1 + (a/b)^2}{1 - (a/b)^2} = p \frac{b}{b-a} \left\{ \frac{1 + (a/b)^2}{1 + (a/b)} \right\} = p \frac{b}{s} \left\{ \frac{1 + (a/b)^2}{1 + (a/b)} \right\} \quad (6)$$

Il termine tra parentesi graffe nella (6) tende a 1 per $a \rightarrow b$ (spessore sottile) e per $a \rightarrow 0$ (spessore infinito). Assume valore minimo (= 0.828) per $a \approx 0.414b$. Il termine fuori graffa ($p b/s$) sovrastima quindi la tensione cerchiante massima con errore inferiore al 21%. Esso può essere interpretato come la tensione membranale (5) che si avrebbe in un recipiente di spessore reale ($s = b - a$), con raggio medio uguale al raggio esterno del cilindro spesso.

Tubo sottile in pressione

La tensione cerchiante, σ_c , nel tubo sottile in pressione interna è data dalla (5). La tensione assiale (fondi chiusi) è la metà [4]: $\sigma_a = 0.5\sigma_c$. La tensione radiale è nulla: $\sigma_r = -p \approx 0$. Per un tubo lungo L , la variazione di lunghezza $\Delta L = L\varepsilon_a = (L/E)\{\sigma_a - \nu(\sigma_r + \sigma_c)\}$ vale

Figura 3. Pressione interna agente su cilindro: (a) di piccolo spessore; (b) di grosso spessore.

Figura 4. Impatto di membrana sferica in pressione contro piano rigido: (a) inizio impatto; (b) durante l’impatto; (c) confronto tra teoria (in rosso) ed esperimento.

$$\Delta L = L\varepsilon_a = (L/E)\{\sigma_a - \nu(\sigma_r + \sigma_c)\} = \sigma_c L(0.5 - \nu)/E \quad (7)$$

La (7) mostra che la variazione di lunghezza è nulla per coefficiente di Poisson $\nu = 0.5$, come per la gomma (es. tubo da giardino) e molti tessuti biologici molli (es. vene e arterie).

Membrana sferica in pressione contro piano rigido

La membrana sottile in Fig. 4a simula una palla (calcio, basket, volley) che colpisce un piano rigido con velocità V_0 . Assumendo perfetta flessibilità e inestensibilità della membrana, l’orma di contatto in Fig. 4b ha raggio generico $a^2 = R^2 - (R - \delta)^2 \approx 2R\delta$ [5] e area $A = \pi a^2 \approx 2\pi R\delta$. Assumendo pressione costante p , la forza di contatto è $F = pA \approx 2\pi pR\delta$. Integrando la forza tra 0 e δ_{max} (massimo schiacciamento, quando $V = 0$), si ottiene il lavoro $W = \pi p R \delta_{max}$. Uguagliando il lavoro all’energia cinetica iniziale $T = 0.5mV_0^2$, dalle precedenti si ricava (il pedice “max” si riferisce all’istante di arresto contro il piano: $V = 0$)

$$\delta_{max} \propto V_0 \quad A_{max} \propto V_0 \quad a_{max} \propto \sqrt{V_0} \quad (8)$$

La seconda delle (8) è graficata in Fig. 4c (retta rossa) per un pallone da calcio [5]. I cerchietti sono dati sperimentali. Le altre due curve riflettono modelli analitici più evoluti [5]. Per velocità fino a 40 piedi/s, la presente teoria semplificata è in linea con l’esperimento.

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DESIGN OF TRIGONALLY-SYMMETRIC AUXETIC MECHANICAL METAMATERIALS

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Keywords: Auxetic Metamaterials, Poisson's ratio, Finite Element (FE) simulation.

ABSTRACT

Introduction

Mechanical metamaterials are a category of artificially designed materials that display unusual behaviors rarely observed in nature. These include auxetic metamaterials, which are a sub-class of these systems that possess a negative Poisson's ratio. These materials contract laterally under compressive loading and expand globally under tensile loading. These distinctive properties arise from their structural design (geometry) rather than their material composition[1]. This study concerns the development of newly design structures by modifying a hexagonal tessellation [2]—featuring trigonal rotational symmetry—through the addition or removal of ribs, and evaluates their auxetic behavior using parametric Finite Element (FE) simulations.

Figure 1. A schematic shape for the original and newly designed structures: a) The original hexagon, b) Design I, c) Design II, and d) Design III.

Methodology

Three newly designed structures—Design I, II, and III—were developed in this study and are derived from a modified hexagon with sides of length i , j , and k (see Figure 1). The original hexagon has 120° angles between each pair of consecutive sides, while the other interior angles may vary. Design I structures were created by removing both sides of length i (see Figure 1b). Design II structures were formed by eliminating both sides of length j

and adding a diagonal that connects the ends of the removed sides (Figure 1c). Design III structures were generated by removing four sides of lengths i and j , while introducing a diagonal connecting two sides of length j within the original hexagon (Figure 1d). Following the design phase, parametric finite element simulations were conducted with j/i and k/i varying from 0.05 to 3.5, and i held constant, to determine the mechanical properties of each structure.

Results and discussion

The FE simulation results for the Poisson's ratios of the three designed structures, as functions of j/i and k/i , are depicted in Figure 2. As shown in the figure, all three designed structures have the potential to exhibit auxetic behaviour; however, Design III demonstrates a wider range and greater diversity of auxeticity.

Figure 2. The variation of Poisson's ratios as functions of j/i and k/i for the three designed structures: a) Design I, b) Design II, and c) Design III.

Conclusion

The auxetic behaviour of three hexagon-derived structures was investigated in this study. The results indicate that these systems are capable of exhibiting the full theoretical range of isotropic Poisson's ratios in two dimensions, i.e., -1 to $+1$.

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UN TAMPONE ANTIVIBRANTE SENSORIZZATO

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Keywords: *tampone antivibrante, sensore, elastomero piezoelettrico.*

SOMMARIO

Introduzione

I tamponi antivibranti sono dispositivi meccanici impiegati in innumerevoli sistemi meccanici con il compito di attenuare gli urti e gli impatti, ridurre la propagazione di vibrazioni ambientali isolando meccanicamente due sezioni l'una dall'altra. Essi vengono impiegati in tutti quei sistemi dove la propagazione di sollecitazioni meccaniche può essere dannosa per il sistema stesso o per l'utente. I tamponi antivibranti costituiscono soluzioni standardizzate e generalmente disponibili a catalogo, commercializzati in varie forme e dimensioni. Questi dispositivi sono sistemi semplici e prevedono l'impiego di un elastomero di durezza variabile che viene interposto tra due parti rigide.

D'altro canto, a livello industriale, ma non limitatamente ad esso, il crescente interesse del monitoraggio delle condizioni operative per scopi di manutenzione predittiva e sicurezza viene svolto misurando e analizzando le vibrazioni meccaniche sul sistema in punti accessibili attraverso reti di sensori. Integrare la funzionalità dei comuni tamponi antivibranti con proprietà sensoristiche e di monitoraggio condurrebbe a pratiche e semplici soluzioni [1] implementabili in molteplici applicazioni [2].

Questo studio dunque propone lo sviluppo di un tampone antivibrante che ricalca alcune architetture presenti in commercio impiegando, però, un elastomero piezoelettrico di carattere prototipale sviluppato dagli stessi autori [3], creando così non solo un dispositivo di smorzamento ma anche un sensore di monitoraggio delle vibrazioni.

Il dispositivo è costituito da due parti metalliche tra le quali si interpone uno strato di piezopolimero, ottenuto tramite uno specifico processo di casting che combina la polarizzazione e polimerizzazione simultanea di una soluzione di silicone bicomponente (Dow Chemical *Sylgard 184*) e una polvere piezoceramica di BaTiO₃.

Questo studio riporta un modello concettuale del dispositivo, la realizzazione del prototipo in stampo e una serie di test sperimentali in frequenza. Questi ultimi dimostrano la funzionalità del dispositivo che a fronte di sollecitazioni meccaniche fornisce un segnale di tensione elettrica monotono crescente in funzione della forza e della repentinà della sollecitazione meccanica imposta.

L'impiego di un materiale intelligente permette di sensorizzare un dispositivo che, malgrado la sua semplicità, si distingue per l'elevato livello di standardizzazione ed elevata economicità.

Modello concettuale

Il dispositivo proposto, raffigurato in sezione in Figura 1, ha un'architettura semplice composta da tre elementi: due parti metalliche (*a* e *b* in Figura 1) e il piezo-elastomero interposto tra esse (*c* in Figura 1). La geometria conica, già implementata in alcuni tamponi presenti in commercio, favorisce l'allineamento degli assi delle varie parti del dispositivo durante il funzionamento.

Figura 1. Modello concettuale: vista in sezione.

Il principio di funzionamento è basato sulle proprietà dell'elastomero che, sollecitato assialmente, polarizza elettricamente le due parti metalliche in modo differenziale dando luogo a un potenziale elettrico misurabile. Il segnale misurato è indice dell'intensità delle sollecitazioni subite. Al contempo, il materiale silicónico, grazie alle sue proprietà di basso modulo elastico ed l'elevata isteresi, smorza efficacemente le vibrazioni.

Prototipazione e test

Il dispositivo è stato realizzato mediante un processo di colatura in stampo a cielo aperto dedicato, alla quale sono seguite due fasi simultanee di polimerizzazione della matrice silicónica e di polarizzazione delle particelle piezoceramiche di BaTiO₃. Lo stampo è stato realizzato da una base plastica (*c* in Figura 2a) elettricamente isolante che funge da appoggio isolando il sistema dall'ambiente circostante. La cavità è prettamente formata dalle due parti metalliche (*a* e *b*) poste alla distanza prescritta mediante un elemento in poliuretano (*d*) termoplastico (TPU) che permette anche di sigillare la cavità ed evitare perdite. Il sistema è mantenuto in posizione mediante un bullone centrale durante il processo.

(a) (b)
Figura 2. a. Prototipazione tramite casting, polarizzazione e polimerizzazione. b. allestimento delle prove sperimentali

La soluzione al 50% in peso di BaTiO₃, immersa nella matrice siliconica inizialmente liquida (*e*), viene colata nella cavità stampo. Le parti metalliche, oltre a fungere da pareti della cavità, costituiscono gli elettrodi polarizzatori della polvere ceramica una volta collegati ad un alimentatore ad alta tensione impostato a 8 kV per tutta la durata del processo di polimerizzazione: 30 ore a temperatura ambiente (i.e. 25°C).

La caratterizzazione sperimentale è stata svolta su una macchina di prova MTS (in Figura 2b): sono stati effettuati test ciclici in compressione sia in presenza che in assenza di grasso lubrificante nell'interfaccia parte metallica-elastomero. E' stato simultaneamente acquisita la differenza di potenziale elettrico tra le facce metalliche applicando un carico resistivo tramite una scheda di acquisizione sincronizzata con la macchina di prova. Nello specifico i test in compressione ciclica hanno previsto:

1. Test di compressione in frequenza a 1, 3 e 5 Hz imponendo ampiezze pari a 0.5, 0.75 e 1.00 mm. Carico resistivo pari a 1 MOhm.
2. Test di sweep lineare in frequenza da 1 a 30 Hz imponendo ampiezze pari a 0.125 e 0.25 mm. Carico resistivo pari a 3.3 MOhm.

Risultati

Figura 3 riporta una matrice dei segnali di tensione misurati nelle prove a frequenza costante in assenza di lubrificante. La presenza di lubrificante, caso qui non riportato, riduce di circa dieci volte il segnale. Si nota come all'aumentare dell'ampiezza, e quindi di forza applicata, la tensione aumenti. Ancora più evidente è l'incremento del segnale di tensione all'aumentare della frequenza: una variazione repentina della differenza di carica elettrica determina un picco di tensione più elevato a parità di carico applicato e carico resistivo.

Figura 3. Tensione output a 1,3 e 5 Hz di frequenza di eccitazione in condizioni non lubrificate.

Figura 4 riporta i risultati ottenuti nello sweep test lineare. Nello specifico Figura 4a riporta il segnale di tensione RMS al variare della frequenza di eccitazione ottenuto imponendo un'ampiezza di sollecitazione pari a 0.25 mm (in rosso) e 0.125 mm (in verde). Figura 4b riporta l'assorbimento energetico percentuale del materiale in funzione della

frequenza di eccitazione. Anche in questo caso si nota come l'aumento in frequenza vada ad amplificare il segnale. In aggiunta lo smorzamento delle vibrazioni dovuto alla natura elastomerica del materiale, viene confermato dall'elevata dissipazione energetica riscontrata su un'ampia banda di frequenze (Figura 4b),.

Figura 4.a. Tensione voltaica RMS in funzione della frequenza di eccitazione per tutte le prove. **b.** Dissipazione energetica del materiale in funzione della frequenza di eccitazione.

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Influenza della Caratterizzazione dei Materiali tramite Prove di Torsione sull'Accuratezza delle Simulazioni FEM nel Processo di Estrusione

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Keywords: Test di torsione, Caratterizzazione del materiale, Processo di Estrusione, Simulazione FEM, Flow stress

SOMMARIO

Introduzione

Negli ultimi anni, l'uso dei codici agli Elementi Finiti (FEM) è divenuto centrale nella progettazione e ottimizzazione dei processi di formatura dei metalli, come l'estrusione dell'alluminio. L'accuratezza di tali simulazioni dipende fortemente dalla corretta modellazione del comportamento plastico del materiale [1,2]. In questo contesto, il test di torsione a caldo si è dimostrato particolarmente efficace per caratterizzare le curve di tensione-deformazione del materiale fino ad elevati livelli di deformazione, tipici delle condizioni a cui viene sottoposto nei processi di deformazione plastica dei metalli.

Problema affrontato

Il lavoro si focalizza sull'impatto che ha la caratterizzazione meccanica del materiale, tramite prove di torsione a caldo, sull'accuratezza delle simulazioni FEM, in un processo industriale di estrusione. Sono state testate quattro leghe di alluminio nominalmente appartenenti alla classe AA6082 e alla condizione O di omogeneizzazione, ma provenienti da quattro distinti lotti di colata, indicate rispettivamente come Lega 1, Lega 2, Lega 3 e Lega 4. Il problema affrontato mostra come variazioni minime nella composizione chimica e nei cicli termici di omogeneizzazione possano influenzare le proprietà di flowstress (o tensione di flusso) del materiale, e di conseguenza i risultati delle simulazioni numeriche dei processi.

Materiali e Metodi – Prove di torsione a caldo

I provini, cilindrici pieni con un diametro e una lunghezza del tratto utile pari a 10 mm [Fig. 1], sono stati riscaldati per induzione a una velocità di 1°C/s e mantenuti alla temperatura

desiderata per 5 minuti [3]. Per permettere il controllo preciso della temperatura nel provino è presente un foro di diametro 3 mm e lunghezza 52.5 mm, all'interno del quale viene posta una termocoppia che possa registrare la temperatura in un punto prossimo al tratto utile. Il controllo della temperatura è gestito tramite un regolatore PID collegato alla termocoppia. I test sono stati eseguiti a tre temperature (450°C, 500°C, 550°C) e tre velocità di deformazione (0.1 s⁻¹, 1 s⁻¹, 10 s⁻¹).

Fig. 1 a) Geometria del provino cilindrico (in mm); b) Foto di un provino AA6082 durante la prova di torsione a caldo, effettuate presso l'Università di Bologna - DIN.

Dal test di torsione, gli output forniti dalla macchina sono la coppia [N·mm] e l'angolo di torsione [rad] applicato al provino. In seguito, è stato utilizzato il modello di Fields-Backofen [4] per calcolare la deformazione a taglio γ e lo sforzo a taglio τ [MPa], in modo da considerare la deformazione, la tensione e la velocità di deformazione riferite al diametro esterno del provino di torsione, come indicato nelle Eq.1, 2 e 3.

$$\gamma = \frac{R \theta}{L}, \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{\gamma} = \frac{R \dot{\theta}}{L}, \quad (2)$$

$$\tau = \frac{M}{2 \pi R^3} (3 + n + m), \quad (3)$$

Dove M è il momento torcente [N·mm], L è la lunghezza del tratto utile del provino [mm] e R il raggio [mm].

Numerosi studi hanno dimostrato che l'incrudimento generato dalla deformazione e la sensibilità alla velocità di deformazione hanno effetti trascurabili sulle leghe di alluminio nel calcolo della tensione, in quanto la loro influenza sul comportamento del materiale ad alte temperature è minima [1,2]. Di conseguenza, in questo studio sono stati trascurati i coefficienti m e n, ottenendo la tensione e la deformazione equivalenti di Von Mises, come da Eq. 4 e 5.

$$\bar{\sigma} = \frac{M 3\sqrt{3}}{2 \pi R^3}, \quad (4)$$

$$\bar{\epsilon} = \frac{\gamma}{\sqrt{3}}. \quad (5)$$

Materiali e Metodi – Simulazioni FEM dell'estrusione

Le curve $\bar{\sigma}$ [MPa] – $\bar{\epsilon}$ sono state utilizzate come dati di input per simulazioni FEM di un processo industriale di estrusione, realizzate con il software QForm UK®. L'attività sperimentale ha previsto l'estrusione di tre profili tubolari, con diametro esterno di 40 mm e spessore di 4 mm, realizzati utilizzando la lega denominata Lega 1 [Fig. 2]. Il confronto tra risultati numerici e sperimentali ha permesso di valutare l'accuratezza delle simulazioni in termini di carico di estrusione, velocità di estrusione e temperatura di uscita del profilo.

Fig. 2 Simulazione del processo di estrusione con QForm Extrusion UK®. a) mesh di pezzo e utensili; b) distribuzione della temperatura [°C]; c) velocità nella direzione z [mm/s]

Risultati – Caratterizzazione del materiale

Le curve ottenute mostrano significative differenze tra le leghe [Fig. 3]. La Lega 1 ha evidenziato una maggiore resistenza alla deformazione, la Lega 3 un marcato fenomeno di softening, mentre la Lega 4 una minore duttilità. I risultati confermano, quindi, l'influenza delle caratteristiche microstrutturali, derivanti da differenze di fornitura o trattamento, sul comportamento plastico.

Fig. 3 Curve sperimentali σ - ϵ della Lega 1, 2, 3 e 4.

Risultati – Simulazioni di estrusione

Sono state effettuate quattro differenti simulazioni numeriche del processo di estrusione. In ogni simulazione, tutti i parametri del modello e dei tool e del materiale sono stati tenuti costanti, variando solamente il flow stress del materiale in base alla lega. L'errore sul carico massimo di estrusione è stato del 2% per la Lega 1 (rispetto ai dati sperimentali), ma ha raggiunto fino al 21% per le altre leghe. La velocità del profilo è risultata poco sensibile alle variazioni del materiale, con un errore inferiore all'1% per tutti i casi. Le temperature in uscita hanno mostrato un'oscillazione dell'errore tra il 1.5% e il 4%.

Discussione e commento finale

I risultati mostrano come variazioni marginali nella composizione o nel ciclo termico dei materiali AA6082, pur entro le tolleranze della norma, possano avere un impatto non trascurabile sull'accuratezza delle simulazioni FEM. L'integrazione delle curve sperimentali ottenute da torsione a caldo permette una modellazione più realistica e rappresenta un valido strumento per il controllo qualità e la selezione dei materiali nella produzione industriale.

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NUMERICAL MODELING OF MICRO-SCALE SURFACE FEATURE REPLICATION IN PLASTIC INJECTION MOLDING

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ABSTRACT

Introduction

Computer-Aided Engineering (CAE) tools such as Moldflow® are widely used to simulate injection molding at the macroscale. However, their accuracy drops significantly at the microscale, where phenomena like wall slip, surface tension, and scale-dependent viscosity dominate flow behavior. These effects, intensified by the high surface-to-volume ratio, are not adequately captured by standard models [1]. Wall slip becomes critical in micro-features, where high shear rates and thermal gradients cause the melt to slide along mold walls. Yao et al. [2] showed that for submicron features, slip significantly alters flow behavior, requiring advanced models. Similarly, surface tension plays a key role, as capillary forces can lead to incomplete filling or air entrapment [3]. Despite these limitations, some studies have adapted macroscopic CAE tools for micro-feature simulation. Brulez et al.[4] and Rytka et al. [5] used hybrid meshing by importing fine COMSOL meshes into Moldflow, achieving better accuracy. Coarse meshes led to overestimated filling, stressing the need for finer resolution at the microscale. Thermal parameters further affect simulation reliability. The heat transfer coefficient H_{tc} varies widely due to surface roughness, contact area, and trapped air—from 500–1000 $W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot K^{-1}$ [10,11] to 30,000 $W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot K^{-1}$ [4, 5]. Calibration is often needed. Likewise, the no-flow temperature T_{no} , which defines when polymer flow stops, differs from standard transition points. For amorphous polymers, it lies 20–70 K above T_g while for semicrystalline, it lies 10–80 K below T_m [5]. To overcome these challenges, we propose a hybrid simulation approach combining Moldflow for macroscopic flow with COMSOL Multiphysics® for micro-feature zones. This strategy enhances accuracy in predicting replication ratios and flow front behavior in micro-injection molding.

Materials and Methods

The polymer used is TOPAS 5013L-10, a cyclic olefin copolymer (COC) known for its excellent replication fidelity and low shrinkage. Key thermal and rheological properties were extracted from the Moldflow database. The no-flow temperature (T_{no}), a critical parameter for modeling solidification, was experimentally determined to be 160°C using the Melt Flow Index (MFI) method, following the procedure described in the paper by Rytka et al. [5]. The AISI 316 stainless steel insert was mirror-polished and laser-etched with three conical holes using a picosecond laser (532 nm, spiral pattern, 150 passes). Holes were placed along the flow path to assess replication near and far from the gate. The insert was ultrasonically cleaned in acetic acid and isopropanol. Since profilometry couldn't reliably measure depth, a duplicate insert was cross-sectioned and polished, revealing a conical shape (120 μm top diameter, 28 μm bottom, 80 μm depth) used for simulation modeling. Micro-injection molding was performed using the prepared mold insert to produce 18 mm diameter, 1.5 mm thick discs with three replicated micro-pins. Mold temperatures (T_{mold} = 60, 100, 120 °C) and injection velocities (v_{inj} = 25, 50, 100 mm/s) were varied, with a fixed melt temperature of 260 °C and no holding pressure. Pin heights were measured using a Keyence microscope, and replication ratio was calculated as the percentage of the replicated height relative to the 80 μm mold cavity depth.

Figure 1 (Up) The injection molded disc with its feed system. (Down) The proposed 2D model in COMSOL with the applied boundary conditions.

Simulations used a 3D mesh with fine refinement around microfeatures. Material properties and processing conditions matched experiments, including a no-flow temperature of 160°C and a heat transfer coefficient of 30,000 W/(m²·K) [4, 5]. The fill phase was modeled with small time steps to capture microfeature filling. Despite this, Moldflow predicted full filling, unlike the partial replication observed experimentally.

As can be seen in **Figure 1**, 2D cross-sectional model of the pin was developed in COMSOL Multiphysics® 6.1, using a 0.5 mm × 0.5 mm domain centered on the pin, extracted from the macro part. The pin geometry was modeled as a trapezoidal cavity (120 μm base, 28 μm top, 80 μm height). The domain was split into polymer and air regions, with properties assigned accordingly. Polymer viscosity was defined using the Cross-WLF model, with thermal and rheological data imported from Moldflow. The no-flow temperature was set at 160°C to simulate solidification. The simulation coupled laminar flow, heat transfer, and interface tracking using the phase field method, which allowed accurate modeling of the polymer-air interface and surface tension dynamics. Boundary conditions were derived from macro-scale Moldflow results, with velocity and temperature profiles applied at the inlet. A no-slip

velocity condition was imposed at the mold wall based on low shear stress (<0.09 MPa), remaining below the threshold for slip. Convective heat fluxes were applied at all boundaries, with calibrated heat transfer coefficients (1000 W/m²·K for mold/polymer interface, 2000 W/m²·K for the polymer/polymer interface and 15 W/m²·K at the air outlet). Simulations were run for two contact angles (90° and 135°) to assess wettability effects on replication. This setup enabled high-fidelity modeling of micro-feature filling, capturing the combined influence of thermal gradients, viscosity changes, and interfacial forces on polymer flow.

Results and Discussion

Replication ratio (RR) increased with both mold temperature and injection velocity, as shown in **Figure 2**. At low mold temperature (60°C), even high injection velocities failed to produce good replication, with RR staying below 65%. In contrast, at 100°C (within the recommended range), RR values between 45% and 70% were achieved even at low velocity, and at 120°C , replication plateaued around 85%, indicating diminishing returns beyond this point. Distance from the gate also affected replication. At 60°C and 100°C , pins farther from the gate showed higher RR, likely due to longer residence time and viscous heating. Near the gate, rapid pressure drop limited filling. However, at 120°C , this positional trend disappeared, and replication became uniform across all pins, suggesting that higher mold temperatures homogenize the filling behavior and reduce sensitivity to flow path and pressure loss.

Figure 2 Experimental RR% as a function of V_{inj} , pin distance and T_{mold}

Moldflow consistently overpredicted replication, showing full filling of microfeatures regardless of process conditions. Despite a refined mesh and conservative heat transfer settings, its coarse time-stepping and lack of microscale physics—like surface tension and capillary effects—limit its accuracy for microscale replication.

Figure 3 Experimental/numerical pin shape and height comparison ($T_{mold}=60^\circ\text{C}$ and $V_{inj}=50\text{mm/s}$)

Regarding the COMSOL simulations results, simulations with a hydrophobic contact angle ($\theta_s = 135^\circ$) reproduced the experimental pin shape accurately, capturing the curvature and profile of the advancing flow front (**Figure 3**). However, as can be seen in **Figure 4**, they consistently underestimated the pin height, particularly at higher temperatures, due to the static nature of the contact angle, which does not account for dynamic wetting behavior

during filling. Simulations with a neutral contact angle ($\theta_s = 90^\circ$) predicted greater wetting and higher filling levels (**Figure 4**), aligning more closely with the experimental pin heights. However, the resulting pin shapes deviated significantly from the experimental observations, suggesting that the model overestimated wetting by neglecting the mold's hydrophobic character. COMSOL captured the overall experimental trends—higher replication with increased velocity and temperature—but deviations in absolute values point to the need for dynamic contact angle modeling. Static angles alone fail to capture both shape and height, emphasizing the importance of accurately modeling wetting dynamics and polymer-wall interactions in microscale simulations.

Figure 4 Experimental vs. Numerical Height Comparison Under All Test Conditions

Conclusion

This study highlights the effectiveness of a two-step simulation approach for predicting microstructure replication in injection molding. Moldflow alone lacked the resolution to capture microscale effects, but when its results were used as boundary conditions in COMSOL, key phenomena like surface tension and wetting behavior were accurately represented. Reliable replication predictions depended on careful modeling of contact angle, surface tension, and no-flow temperature. The combined method offers a more accurate and practical tool for optimizing micro-injection molding processes.

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Femtosecond laser structuring of lithium-ion battery electrodes: parameter optimisation for anode and cathode

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ABSTRACT

Introduction

The growing demand for high-energy lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) in the automotive sector is driving the development of novel manufacturing techniques to improve battery performance. Since their discovery in 2019, the design of LIBs for the automotive sector has been faced with a challenge between balancing high energy density and high-power density, enabling high capacity and fast charging and discharging respectively [1]. Laser structuring is a novel technique that has shown improvements on battery performance by controlling the tortuosity of the material, leading to an improved diffusion of Li-ions through electrode interfaces. Laser patterned microstructures limit the electrolyte concentration gradients, reducing the electrochemical overpotentials that lead to lithium plating, enabling fast charging [2]. Specifically, the implementation of ultra-short pulsed lasers can improve battery performance by achieving higher precision and improved structural quality, compared to short pulse lasers. This work investigates the effect of laser parameters using a femtosecond pulsed-wave laser to structure three types of electrode materials: pure graphite and graphite with high silicon content for the anode, and lithium iron phosphate (LFP) for the cathode. Silicon-enhanced anodes are of particular interest due to their significantly higher theoretical capacity. By systematically tuning laser parameters of each material, this study aims to optimise structuring quality and lay the groundwork for evaluating its impact on electrochemical performance. The obtained results contribute to the development of scalable-high performance LIBs, supporting future integration of laser electrode structuring in industrial battery production lines.

Methods

Three lithium-ion battery electrode materials were tested where all electrodes were provided as a layer of active material on a foil of current collector. Specifically, an LFP cathode where the active layer measured 90 μm in thickness and the aluminium foil measured 18 μm . Two electrode materials were tested for the anode, both made with copper foil measuring 11 μm in thickness. The active layer of graphite measured 70 μm while the anode containing graphite and silicon measured 30 μm in thickness. A femtosecond pulsed wave laser with emission wavelength of 1030nm, spot diameter of 15 μm and maximum pulse energy of 100 μJ was

employed for the experiments. The electrode films were prepared as 2 x 3 cm samples and held onto a glass slide to remain flat and in tension, preventing any defocusing issues. The structuring parameters were chosen with the aim of evaluating the effect of fluence, determined as the product of irradiance and interaction time. The interaction time represents the duration where the laser beam remains within the spot diameter. With a range between 57 and 1 J/cm², 9 levels of fluence were chosen. Fluence levels were achieved by combining three levels of frequency (60kHz, 200kHz and 1000kHz) with three levels of average power (1.5W, 3W and 6W). Each level of fluence was performed with three different number of pulses: 50, 100 and 150. Detailed process parameters are summarised in Table 1, where each experiment was repeated three times, for a total of 243 experiments.

Table 1: Parameters for anode and cathode femtosecond laser structuring

Experiment	Frequency (kHz)	Power (W)	Fluence (J/cm ²)
1	60	6	56.62
2		3	28.31
3		1.5	14.15
4	200	6	16.99
5		3	8.49
6		1.5	4.25
7	1000	6	3.40
8		3	1.7
9		1.5	0.85

The geometry of the laser structuring is portrayed in Figure 2, where each set was conducted at three fixed levels of frequency. Across each set, the average power and the number of pulses were varied, leading to an efficient processing method.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of structuring geometry conducted at 60kHz, 200kHz and 1000kHz, across three electrode materials.

The analysis of the experiments was conducted with a wave runner interferometer from DV Optics that allows for 3-dimensional images to be obtained with an accuracy of 1 μm. Specifically, a scan of the structured electrode surface was conducted for all experiments, allowing for both diameter and depth to be measured. To ensure consistency, scans were

conducted with the same lighting and imaging settings. Both diameter and depth were manually measured from the scans through the associated InterferoLab Software.

Results

The measured hole diameters and depths at equivalent laser parameters showed different behaviours across the three electrode materials, as shown in Fig. 2. Fluence has a similar effect for both diameter and depth, where increasing fluence increases both the diameter and the depth for all materials. However, distinct differences in response to equal parameters were observed. As shown in Fig. 2a, high-Si graphite exhibited the largest hole diameter at fluences $<17 \text{ J/cm}^2$, being the most electrically conductive of the materials. This is attributed to the higher thermal conductivity of silicon nanoparticles as well as the thin active layer of $30 \mu\text{m}$, compared to the $70 \mu\text{m}$ in pure graphite and $90 \mu\text{m}$ in LFP.

Figure 2: Diameters (a) and depths (b) against fluence, with 50 pulses per hole, resulting average and standard deviation from three characterised holes per parameter combination.

In contrast, Fig. 2b shows that high-Si graphite produced the shallowest holes under the same conditions, while pure graphite and LFP showed similar and deeper depths. For instance, at fluence of 8.5 J/cm^2 , the depth on high-Si graphite was $28 \mu\text{m}$, compared to the $57 \mu\text{m}$ and $75 \mu\text{m}$ depth of pure graphite and LFP respectively. It is therefore concluded that the thickness of the material exhibits an important role on the optimisation of laser parameters. In fact, high-Si graphite exhibits an energy distribution parallel to the surface, leading to wider but less deep holes. For thicker materials of pure graphite and LFP, the energy was absorbed more orthogonally to the surface, resulting in narrower and deeper holes.

To assess the effect of number of pulses per holes, three different levels from 50 to 150 were tested. As shown in Fig.3, as the number of pulses per hole is increased, both diameter and depths increase. However, based on the results of this study, different progressions are observed per each material. According to the literature, graphite exhibits an asymptotic progression, most evident at higher number of pulses per hole. [3] The behavior is attributed to the cone shaped holes created during the continuous drilling. This results in a grater surface area exposed by the laser beam. The same phenomenon is observed for high-Si graphite, where results are significant up to a depth of $35 \mu\text{m}$. At higher pulse numbers, the laser

structuring penetrated through the active layer and the current collector, leading to complete drilling. Hence, those results were discarded. Lastly, the progression exhibited by LFP shows an exponential trend, where at lower number of pulses the diameter stays unvaried, indicating high quality holes.

Figure 3: Influence of the number of pulses on the resulting diameters and depths in laser structuring of graphite (a) and high-Si-graphite (b) anodes and LFP cathode (c).

This parameter optimisation led to the tuning of laser parameters for three electrode materials with different composition and thicknesses, laying the groundwork for optimised structuring of coin cells to evaluate the electrochemical performance of structured electrodes.

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3D copper current collector by laser texturing for quick zinc metal plating

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ABSTRACT

Introduction

Zinc-ion batteries (ZIBs) are gaining traction as a safer and more cost-effective alternative to lithium-ion batteries, primarily due to their use of non-flammable aqueous electrolytes and the natural abundance of zinc [1]. In addition, their high energy density and the fact that, for example, Zn-ion batteries' operating voltage (2V) is lower than Li-ion batteries' (4V) make it a desirable substitute for other metal-based systems.

However, a significant challenge in ZIBs is the formation of zinc dendrites during metal plating onto current collectors (CCs), which compromises both battery performance and safety. Since CCs are crucial for facilitating electron flow between electrodes and external circuits, their effectiveness directly impacts the performance of zinc-based batteries. Traditional flat (2D) copper foils often result in uneven zinc deposition and dendrite growth under high current densities.

Laser-based surface structuring presents a promising solution by enabling the engineering of three-dimensional (3D) textures that guide uniform metal plating, reduce local current density, and enhance electrochemical performance. While prior research has demonstrated the benefits of laser-induced micro/nano-structuring in lithium-ion systems, its application to ZIBs remains largely unexplored [2–7].

Thus, this study explores the use of laser-textured three-dimensional (3D) copper current collectors by using a picosecond laser to mitigate dendrite formation and enable high-rate zinc deposition, paving the way for the development of anode-free ZIBs.

In particular, the linear patterning approach offers scalability for mass production and may enhance recyclability by promoting the preferential orientation of delamination cracks [8,9].

Materials and Methods

Commercial 100 μm thick copper foils were cut into 60 \times 40 mm² samples and chemically cleaned. Laser texturing was performed using an ultrashort-pulsed (10 ps) laser at 1064 nm wavelength. A Raylase Superscan V galvanometric scanning head was used to scan the laser, and an F-theta lens focuses the beam to a waist diameter of about 10 μm at $1/e^2$ intensity.

A parallel-line pattern with a 30 μm pitch was chosen, considering the beam size and the proposed objective of increasing the surface area further. Different grooves of three different depths were obtained: 5 μm (5LT), 10 μm (10LT), and 15 μm (15LT). The laser parameters were optimized to ensure consistent groove morphology and minimal thermal damage: 500 kHz of repetition rate, 30 μm line spacing, 1000 mm/s of scan speed, 4-10-15 passes, 6 W of power, corresponding to 12 μJ energy per pulse and 15.3 J/cm² of fluence.

Zinc was electrochemically deposited onto the textured and untextured copper substrates using a 0.5 M ZnSO₄·7H₂O aqueous electrolyte. Two deposition protocols were tested: 10 mA/cm² for 20 minutes and 20 mA/cm² for 10 minutes. A three-electrode setup with a graphite counter electrode and Ag/AgCl reference electrode was used. Post-deposition, samples were stored in an argon atmosphere.

Surface morphology was analyzed using optical and digital microscopy, and scanning electron microscopy (SEM), while elemental composition was assessed via energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). Voltage profiles during deposition were recorded using a potentiostat to evaluate electrochemical behavior.

Results and Discussion

SEM images revealed that laser-textured surfaces exhibited well-defined grooves with minimal heat-affected zones. The grooves were filled with laser-induced periodic surface structures (LIPSS), enhancing surface roughness and potentially improving zinc adhesion, see Figure 1-a) and b). Zinc deposition on untextured copper was uneven and prone to oxidation, while laser-textured surfaces promoted uniform plating, Figure 1-c) and d).

EDS mapping confirmed that laser texturing significantly improved the uniformity and coverage of zinc on the copper surface. Quantitative analysis showed higher zinc content and reduced oxygen presence on textured samples, particularly for the 10LT configuration. The 15LT samples showed diminishing returns, suggesting an optimal groove depth around 10 μm .

Table 1. Percentage mass of elements.

		%O	%Cu	%Zn
10mA20min	As is	31.82 \pm 1.52	2.84 \pm 0.1	65.86 \pm 1.66
	Cu LT5	8.96 \pm 0.46	3.71 \pm 0.12	87.33 \pm 2.21
	Cu LT10	8.92 \pm 0.92	2.77 \pm 0.09	88.31 \pm 2.23
	Cu LT15	19.15 \pm 0.9	1.08 \pm 0.1	79.77 \pm 2.2
20mA10min	As is	21.83 \pm 1.12	14.31 \pm 0.38	63.86 \pm 1.62
	Cu LT5	32.73 \pm 1.56	1.92 \pm 0.07	65.35 \pm 1.66
	Cu LT10	18.58 \pm 0.92	2.56 \pm 0.09	78.86 \pm 2.00
	Cu LT15	25.59 \pm 1.2	13.16 \pm 0.5	61.24 \pm 2.0

Figure 1. SEM morphology of the (a) untreated and the (b) LT5 sample; Zinc deposition at 20mA for 10 minutes on (c) untreated material and (d) LT5.

Voltage profiles at 10 mA/cm² indicated that deeper textures (especially 15LT) required less overpotentials, suggesting that increased surface area has altered nucleation dynamics. At higher current densities (20 mA/cm²), the trend is inverted: only the less pronounced texturing finds a chemical balance, and the differences between textured and untextured samples become more pronounced, with textured samples showing more stable and uniform deposition behavior.

Figure 2. Voltage profiles of Zinc deposition at 10 and 20 mA/cm².

Conclusions

This study demonstrates that laser-induced 3D texturing of copper current collectors can effectively enhance zinc deposition uniformity with the final aim of suppressing dendrite

formation, even under high current densities (up to 20 mA/cm²). The optimal groove depth was found to be 10 μm, balancing processing time and electrochemical performance. These findings support the feasibility of using laser-structured CCs in next-generation anode-free ZIBs and potentially in other metal-based battery systems such as lithium and sodium-ion batteries.

Further research will focus on integrating these textured CCs into full-cell configurations and evaluating long-term cycling stability under practical operating conditions. Scaling up the laser texturing process for industrial applications and exploring alternative pattern geometries are also key directions.

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Masi Contribution to symbolic notation for mechanism design

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ABSTRACT

Mechanism modeling is essential still today for the formulation of efficient design and analysis procedures mainly in catalogs and classifications. Symbolic notation is the basis of mathematical formulation that has been proposed since the beginning of the nineteenth century during which several solutions were proposed mainly due to Babbage, Willis and Reuleaux. Masi gave fundamental contributions for modern developments with results also in classifications and evaluation of mechanism varieties. Main aspects of Masi contribution to the symbolic notation are discussed with practical results in classification of mechanisms.

Introduction

Modeling is still fundamental today for the analysis and design of mechanisms using approaches and formulations that adapt to the available techniques. Of particular importance is the symbolic notation that allows to synthetically indicate structures and phenomenology that are fundamental for the identification and evaluation of the design and functional characteristics of mechanisms. Mechanism classification in the 18th and 19th centuries was motivated by the variety of designed machines and practical applications, [1]. Monge, Laboulaye, Babbage, Hachette, Reuleaux, Grashof, Willis, Masi, Silvester, and some others gradually developed modern notations for typical components and their functions for design and operation purposes. Charles Babbage (1791–1871) can be considered an early pioneer in the invention of modern symbolic notation with even early publication specific on the subject in 1826, [2]. Later Robert Willis (1800–1875) proposed a set of motion lines to represent the motion of bodies, [3]. In his 1875 book, [4] Franz Reuleaux (1829–1905) considered a machine as a chain or network of constrained links and the key to distinguishing one machine from another was the assembly of joint pairs that formulated with formulas. Francesco Masi (1852–1944), [5], in 1883 in his 1883 book [6] elaborated a mechanism classification by using a revision of Reuleaux's approach and formalism in [4].

Masi Francesco: biographical notes, [5, 8]

Francesco Masi, Fig. 1, was born on 28 February 1852 in Guastalla (Reggio Emilia). He got the engineering degree in 1875 at the Royal School of Engineering in Turin. His first employment in 1875 was as professor of Physics and Mechanics at the Technical College in Cagliari. In 1877 he went back to Bologna to the Royal School of Engineering as assistant professor in the field of Mechanics of Machinery. In 1891 he was appointed full professor at

Bologna University where he remained until his death that occurred on 30 November 1944 in Bologna. He succeeded to Giuseppe Barilli (Quirico Filopanti), [7], who seems not having had any relationship with Masi. He got married with the daughter Teresa of famous Italian poet Giosuè Carducci, but they never had children. Francesco Masi addressed his attention to TMM but also to the fields of Hydraulics, Technical Drawing, Mechanics of Agricultural Machines by developing teaching activity in Technical Colleges and at Bologna University.

Francesco Masi addressed great attention to teaching activity in the frames both of university formation of engineers and Technical Colleges for technicians. He started his career by giving classes at a Technical College in Cagliari. He devoted his efforts mainly to the subjects of Technical Drawing and Machine Design in the Technical College Aldini-Valeriani in Bologna until 1906, [9].

Figure 1. Portrait of Francesco Masi (1852-1944): a) young; b) at a mature age; c) old time

His main contribution, still of modern significance, can be recognized in the rigorous systematization of Reuleaux classification of mechanisms together with an analytical approach for analysis and synthesis of mechanisms. He has also contributed to standardization of Technical Drawings, development of Agricultural Machines, and to first work on Lubrication and Tribology. His work has been an inspiration for many generations in Italy and still is considered as an interesting source

Masi contribution to analysis with symbolic notation

Relevant is the improvement that Masi elaborated in [6] for the mechanism classification by using Reuleaux' s approach and formalism in [4]. Masi revised and completed the mechanism notation by expressing the following formalism: type symbols for general design characteristics of bodies, like for example C is for cylinder, P is for prismatic box, Rd is for geared wheel; shape symbols for the specific geometry of the body, like for example C⁺ is for bulk cylinder (pivot), C⁻ is for hole cylinder (bearing), P⁺ is for bulk prismatic box (slider), P⁻ is for prismatic guide; relationship symbols for describing the relations between two elements of a kinematic chain, like for example || is for parallel axes, x is for crossing lines, < is for inclined lines. Therefore, any mechanism can be represented by a formula, when additional signs are used for fixed bodies (segment with dashed lines), elastic bodies

(wave segment), and moving bodies (straight segment), like for example the cases shown in Fig.2

The symbolic notation was an attempt to develop a more analytical representation of mechanisms, avoiding the encumbering mechanism drawings, even with the aim to use it for analysis and synthesis purposes. The notation is attractive also because it can be very synthetic in showing the variety of possibilities of a kinematic chain like in the example of Fig.2 a).

Fig. 2 Notations of mechanisms in [6] for: a) slider-crank linkage; b) belt transmissions

In addition, the formalism of the proposed notation can be considered part of the classification rules, when one considers that the characters/rules of the classification can be expressed as function of the introduced symbols for the fundamental kinematic properties of kinematic design of mechanisms. The basic rules of Masi's classification of mechanisms can be recognized in the concepts of simple and compound mechanisms, kinematic chain and its inversion, categories and classes of mechanisms, [6]. Simple mechanisms are composed of one circuit of linked bodies only; compound mechanisms are those with more circuits of links with even different nature. A category of simple mechanisms is identified by the number of pairs of different types that are in the kinematic chain. Although a wide range of theoretical possibilities, Masi identified 8 categories only, as those of practical engineering interest that are made of articulation joint ($C+ = C-$ or $P+ = P-$), point with a line ($\alpha.\alpha$), two lines ($a.a$), two screws ($S+ = S-$), two wheels ($R.R$), two gears ($Rd.Rd$), one gear with a pawl ($Rd.a$); compression and traction elements (with a complex notation!). In each category there are

several possible mechanisms that can be grouped in classes with the same kinematic design. By using the above-mentioned concepts and rules Masi classified the mechanisms according to Tables in Fig.3, by starting from the 8 practical simple classes only. He advised that many of the counted mechanisms in the classes can be determined only theoretically (with the help of the notation!) and therefore they should be invented yet. Likewise, extending the consideration to more simple categories with other basic rules/structures, any other mechanisms can be invented, but practical applications should be thought specifically as part of the invention. Thus, he could apply his theory for mechanism classification by giving a unifying view of mechanisms that is also the basis of the systematic organization for teaching mechanism design. He gave also a computation of the design possibility, as reported in Table 2 of Fig.3, in which he calculated up to 25,200 binary mechanisms and 10,362,600 quaternary mechanisms. He also advised that many of the counted mechanisms in the classes can be determined only theoretically (with the help of the notation!) and therefore they should be invented yet.

Category	Number of classes	Description of classes
Homogeneous	8	linkages
Binary	28	wedges and cams, sockets, screws, wheels, gears, ratchets, mechanism by traction and compression
Ternary	56	Gears with sockets, ratchets with gears
Quaternary	70	
5-th	56	
6-th	28	
7-th	8	
8-th	1	

a)

Category	Number of classes	Description of classes
Homogeneous	225	compound linkages, screws, wheels, gears, ratchets, mechanisms by traction and compression
Binary	25,200	gears and linkages, sockets and traction elements, ratchets and gears, ratchets and linkages, linkages and compression systems
Ternary	1,873,200	same as binary
Quaternary	10,362,600	same as binary
...	...	
205-th	1	same as binary

b)

Fig. 3 Classification by Masi 1883: a) simple mechanisms; b) compound mechanisms

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Time-Optimal Trajectory Planning for Anti-Sloshing Robotic Manipulation

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ABSTRACT

Introduction

In many industrial processes it is common to transport containers that are partially filled with liquid. The liquid oscillatory movement inside the container, known as *sloshing*, can cause several problems, including spillage and inconsistent fill levels. This work tackles this problem by developing anti-sloshing pick-and-place trajectories for the simultaneous transport of multiple cylindrical containers. The considered trajectories are 4D SCARA motions (3D translation and 1D rotation about the vertical axis). The goal is to minimize the trajectory duration while keeping the peak reached by the liquid inside each container (hereafter referred as *maximum sloshing height MSH*) under a specified threshold. Existing sloshing-reduction techniques include filters [1], but these are not easily applicable to the case at hand due to the distinct dynamics of each container, besides that they do not constrain the sloshing height during motion, but only at the end of it. Constrained optimization offers a promising alternative, as it allows for trajectory time minimization while directly imposing constraints on the sloshing heights. Although previous work has explored this strategy for a single container or simple motions [2, 3], this study aims to extend it to 4D SCARA motions and multiple containers, a scenario not addressed in the literature. Two families of constrained optimizations are presented. In the first case, the motion law is optimized along a given path, whereas in the second, both the path and the motion law are optimized. Since sloshing constraints must be imposed within an optimization procedure, a reliable and computationally fast sloshing model is needed. The most suitable option is represented by the mass-spring-damper model [2], an equivalent discrete mechanical model which offers a highly efficient sloshing-height

Figure 1. Multi-container.

Figure 2. Setup.

estimation. Based on the approach proposed in [4] for 3D translational motions, the extension to 4D SCARA motions is here presented.

Multi-container configuration and sloshing model

Considering an arbitrary number of identical cylindrical containers mounted in a row on a rigid support (Fig. 1) attached to the robot end-effector, the acceleration $\ddot{\mathbf{r}}_i$ of the i -th container can be expressed as a function of $\ddot{\mathbf{r}}$ (the acceleration of the tray center), and the tray angular velocity $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ and angular acceleration $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$, namely:

$$\ddot{\mathbf{r}}_i = \ddot{\mathbf{r}} + \boldsymbol{\alpha} \times \mathbf{d}_i + \boldsymbol{\omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\omega} \times \mathbf{d}_i). \quad (1)$$

Let R be the radius of the containers, each one of them filled with a liquid of height h and mass m_F . The mass-spring-damper model comprises a rigid mass m_0 that moves rigidly with the container, and a moving mass m_1 , representing the equivalent mass of the first sloshing mode. The mass m_1 is restrained by a damper c_1 and it slides on a paraboloidal surface. The motion of the sloshing mass m_1 of the i -th container is described by the generalized coordinates (x_i, y_i) . Following the same procedure proposed in [4], and adding the dynamic contributions of the tray rotation $\theta(t)$, the following equations of motion can be obtained for the i -th container:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left(1 + \frac{C_1^2}{R^2} x_i^2\right) \ddot{x}_i + \frac{C_1^2}{R^2} x_i y_i \ddot{y}_i = -\frac{C_1^2}{R^2} (x_i^2 + y_i^2) x_i + (2\dot{\theta}_i \dot{y}_i + \dot{\theta}_i^2 x_i + \ddot{\theta}_i y_i) \\ \quad - \omega_1^2 x_i - 2\omega_1 \zeta_1 [\dot{x}_i + \frac{C_1^2}{R^2} (x_i \dot{x}_i + y_i \dot{y}_i) x_i] - \ddot{r}_{i,x} \cos \theta - \ddot{r}_{i,y} \sin \theta - \ddot{r}_{i,z} \frac{C_1}{R} x_i \\ \left(1 + \frac{C_1^2}{R^2} y_i^2\right) \ddot{y}_i + \frac{C_1^2}{R^2} x_i y_i \ddot{x}_i = -\frac{C_1^2}{R^2} (x_i^2 + y_i^2) y_i + (-2\dot{\theta}_i \dot{x}_i + \dot{\theta}_i^2 y_i - \ddot{\theta}_i x_i) \\ \quad - \omega_1^2 y_i - 2\omega_1 \zeta_1 [\dot{y}_i + \frac{C_1^2}{R^2} (x_i \dot{x}_i + y_i \dot{y}_i) y_i] + \ddot{r}_{i,x} \sin \theta - \ddot{r}_{i,y} \cos \theta - \ddot{r}_{i,z} \frac{C_1}{R} y_i \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) can be numerically integrated to obtain the generalized coordinates (x_i, y_i) . From the latter, the MSH of the i -th container $\bar{\eta}_i$ can be computed as [4]:

$$\bar{\eta}_i = \frac{\xi_{11}^2 h m_1}{m_F R} \sqrt{x_i^2 + y_i^2}. \quad (3)$$

Time-optimal trajectory planning: assigned path case

In this case, the path that the tray (and hence the containers) must follow is predefined. Therefore, the optimization objective is to determine the motion law that allows the execution of the trajectory in minimal time, while at the same time binding the sloshing height under a specified threshold in all containers. The path is parameterized in terms of a parameter s , whose motion law $s(t)$, $\dot{s}(t)$, $\ddot{s}(t)$ describes the temporal evolution along the path. The function $\mathbf{r}(s)$ is defined using B-spline basis function, and θ is considered as a linear function of s . Each container motion is therefore uniquely defined by $s(t)$; for this reason the jerk of s is chosen as control input of the problem: $u = \ddot{s}$. If t_{end} is the trajectory duration, the optimization problem can be formulated as¹:

$$\min_{t_{end}, u} \left[\int_0^{t_{end}} (1 + ku^2) dt \right]; \quad (4a)$$

subject to

$$\bar{\eta}_i(t) \leq \bar{\eta}_{lim} \quad i = IC, EC; \quad t \in [0, t_{end}]. \quad (4b)$$

From the constraint inequality in Eq. (4b) it can be seen that the limit is imposed only on the sloshing heights of the two outermost containers IC and EC (Fig. 1). This choice is supported by a large set of simulations, which have shown that constraining only these sloshing heights is sufficient to ensure compliance with the sloshing limits of all containers. This consideration allows the optimization algorithm to be independent of the total number of containers, thus ensuring high application flexibility and limited computation times even in the presence of many containers.

Time-optimal trajectory planning: point-to-point case

This subsection investigates time-optimal trajectory planning along paths that are not completely assigned *a priori*. Only fixed way-volumes, through which optimal paths must pass, are assigned to the optimizer. A path parameter s cannot be used, therefore, the control inputs are: $\mathbf{u}_r = \ddot{\mathbf{r}}$ and $u_\theta = \ddot{\theta}$. The optimization problem is formulated as¹:

$$\min_{t_{end}, \mathbf{u}_r, u_\theta} \left[\int_0^{t_{end}} (1 + k_r \mathbf{u}_r^T \mathbf{u}_r + k_\theta u_\theta^2) dt \right]; \quad (5a)$$

subject to

$$\bar{\eta}_i(t) \leq \bar{\eta}_{lim} \quad i = IC, EC; \quad t \in [0, t_{end}]; \quad (5b)$$

$$\delta^2 \geq (\mathbf{r}(t_j) - \mathbf{r}_j)^T (\mathbf{r}(t_j) - \mathbf{r}_j) \quad j = 1, \dots, n_v. \quad (5c)$$

The passage through n_v way-volumes is imposed in Eq. (5c). Each way-volume is modeled as a sphere of radius δ centered at \mathbf{r}_j , and t_j denotes the time of passage through the j -th sphere, with $t_j \in (0, t_{end})$.

Experimental validation

The experiments use 8 cylindrical containers with a radius $R = 35$ mm, and filled with colored water to a height $h = 40$ mm. The limit imposed on the sloshing height during motion is $\bar{\eta}_{lim} = 15$ mm. The robot chosen for trajectory execution is a 6-DOF *Comau SMART-SiX*. The liquid behavior during motions is recorded using two *GoPro Hero8* cameras attached to the tray. The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 2, where the assigned path used in the

¹Other constraints on the system state are omitted for brevity.

Figure 3. Slushing-height experimental and modeled trends.

first optimization strategy is depicted in blue, while the red line represents the optimized point-to-point path, obtained from the optimizer starting from the green way-volumes. Fig. 3a displays the slushing heights resulting from the assigned-path optimization (blue lines for IC, red for EC; continuous for simulated trends, dashed for experimental trends). The accuracy of the mass-spring-damper model is evident. In contrast, Fig. 3b shows the trends obtained using a non-optimized motion law with a longer duration, highlighting the effectiveness of the optimized motion. Finally, Fig. 3c presents the results of the point-to-point optimization strategy, which not only achieves a shorter motion duration but also demonstrates better compliance with the slushing limits than the assigned-path approach.

Conclusions

This study proposes two time-optimal trajectory planning strategies for the anti-slushing transport of multiple containers, considering 4D SCARA motions. Both strategies led to a significant reduction of the slushing heights compared to the non-optimized case. In particular, the point-to-point strategy proved to be the most effective one, as the optimizer was free to smooth the sharp curves of the path.

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An overview on robotic cable-connector disassembly research

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ABSTRACT

Introduction and problem statement

The growing global production of waste poses an increasing threat to environmental sustainability, with Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) representing a critical and rapidly expanding category. According to the United Nations Institute for Training and Research [1], over 62 billion kilograms of e-waste were generated worldwide in 2022, yet only 22.3 % of this was properly collected and recycled. Much of the remaining waste is either unaccounted for, exported to countries with inadequate recycling infrastructure, or sent to landfills—releasing hazardous pollutants and exacerbating environmental degradation. Even in regions such as Europe, where environmental policies are more advanced, only 42.8 % of WEEE is formally processed [1].

State-of-the-art research in e-waste disassembly currently follows two main directions: general WEEE disassembly [2] and battery pack disassembly [3]. Despite progress, the automation of these processes remain a complex challenge due to the heterogeneity and unpredictable condition of e-waste. Three primary issues must be addressed [2, 3]: (1) assessing the state and residual properties of each item; (2) planning the disassembly process by determining the optimal sequence of operations and appropriate disassembly depth; and (3) executing the required tasks using robots or human workers.

Automatic disassembly offers both long-term and immediate benefits: environmentally, it reduces landfill waste and pollutant emissions; economically, it enhances the profitability and productivity of recycling operations by streamlining the process and improving working conditions for human operators. Additionally, disassembling devices to a sufficient granularity enables the recovery of functioning components for reuse and the extraction of valuable materials from more uniform waste streams.

Despite the fact that emerging solutions leverage advancements in robotics, computer vision, and artificial intelligence, completely automating e-waste disassembly is still not feasible. This is due to the difficulty of automating certain tasks, such as disconnecting press-fit joints, detaching glued or interlocked parts, and safely removing electrical connectors [3]. In fact, robots are well-suited for repetitive and simple tasks, but struggle with operations requiring a combination of dexterity, force control, and adaptive strategies. Consequently, modern solutions employ human-robot

collaborative approaches, leveraging human operators for complex manipulations like the previous ones. However, having human workers in the disassembly process raises issues regarding health risks, ergonomics, and productivity.

In order to move toward greater autonomy in e-waste processing, this article focuses on documenting the current state of the art in automatic cable connector disassembly. To the best of the author’s knowledge, this field remains largely unexplored and as per today cables in electronic waste are typically removed manually—either pulled or cut—exposing the human operators and the potentially reusable internal components to electric shock in case a residual charge remains in batteries or capacitors. This study synthesizes advancements from related domains such as cable connector assembly and inspection to inform robotic disassembly strategies due to the total lack of articles about cable connectors focused on disassembly.

State-of-the-art analysis

To address the disassembly of electrical connectors several sequential steps are required: (1) identifying the connectors, (2) determining their pose, (3) evaluating their reachability, (4) approaching them, (5) grasping them, and (6) extracting them. However, due to the limited scope of this work, the focus is centered on detection and manipulation as macro themes.

The main objective of the detection phase is to determine the number, type, and poses of cable connectors so that, once the locking mechanism between the plug and socket has been identified and an associated target position obtained, the subsequent manipulation phase can proceed efficiently. Current approaches leverage one-stage deep learning object detectors like YOLO [4, 5, 6] and MobileNet-SSD [7], favored for their fast inference and simpler architectures, as well as two-stage methods like Faster R-CNN [8], which offer superior accuracy and sensitivity to fine features. An important limitation of these algorithms is that detection accuracy gets significantly compromised when key features are not clearly distinguishable, there are several similar types of connectors in the scene, and the background is rich in detail. Although most studies conducted to date focus on dealing with a very limited number (fewer than four) of connectors [5, 8, 9], Wang and Johansson [4] have shown that it is possible to obtain acceptable results by training algorithms to recognize twenty connectors, verifying the better performance of YOLOv5 compared to Faster R-CNN in terms of mean Average Precision and precision across a broader class set.

In addition to purely visual methods, some works incorporate 3D model-based detection to either supplement or replace standard vision pipelines. Nguyen et al. [5], for example, use RGB-D images from stereo cameras to detect bounding boxes via YOLOv7, then align the resulting point clouds with CAD models using a proprietary algorithm for classification. Yet 3D data is not always essential; once a connector is localized in 2D, algorithms like MegaPose [10] or direct 2D-to-multi-view projections [7] can be used to estimate its 6D pose. However, disassembly differs significantly from assembly due to the unknown condition of connectors, which may be damaged, dirty, or occluded, making them harder to detect. This is further complicated by limited datasets [4], small connector size, and complex, feature-rich backgrounds.

The manipulation phase in the robotic disassembly of electrical connectors involves disengaging the locking mechanism and extracting the plug. This task requires evaluating the available workspace, the accessibility of the connector, and whether

the connector can be directly approached by the end-effector. Unlike assembly, where manipulation focuses on precise positioning—often using spiral search patterns and compliance strategies to align the plug with the socket—disassembly manipulation typically allows for more direct actions once the locking mechanism is released and friction becomes the only remaining coupling force. In such cases, the connector or even the cable itself may be pulled with fewer concerns about alignment.

However, unplugging the connector is not trivial because of the variety of locking mechanisms that can be encountered like snap-in mechanisms, bayonet mounts, threaded couplings, etc. and the complex grippers required to allow specific motions and end-effector capabilities for each class of connector. For example, in [10], a custom two-finger gripper with specially designed fingernails is used to release the clip of a flexible flat cable connector. Research into cable and connector manipulation during assembly tasks provides valuable insights for disassembly. In [5], two robots equipped with simple parallel-jaw grippers cooperate to successfully assemble wire harnesses. Similarly, [7] employs a dual-arm setup, where one robot repositions the connector to a more favorable pose before the second robot completes the manipulation, highlighting the need for flexible and adaptive strategies in constrained environments. Meanwhile, [9] demonstrates a strategy where the robot grasps the cable instead of the connector itself, reducing spatial constraints and employing curriculum learning to improve insertion control.

Discussion and future research directions

The previous analysis reveals that the current research base is not robust enough to fully support autonomous cable disassembly. Nevertheless, the authors believe that several important insights can still be drawn. The primary objective of cable connector disassembly is to autonomously detach connectors from their sockets and therefore recognizing the locking mechanisms is key. Once the features of the locking mechanism are segmented, it is possible to infer a manipulation strategy.

For this reason, the authors argue that vision-based methods are likely more suitable than 3D model-based approaches. Specifically, 3D methods demand a precise match between virtual models and physical components, meaning that addressing the variability of locking mechanism features necessitates creating an equally extensive set of accurate 3D models. In contrast, vision-based methods offer greater flexibility due to the accuracy and generalization capabilities of neural networks, making them a more practical choice.

From a future development standpoint, it would be appropriate to develop a neural network-based vision system to effectively segment locking mechanism types. Several challenges must be addressed to achieve this goal: (1) creating a proper training database, (2) optimizing calculation times, and (3) completing segmentation with a realistic background. Considering the small size of cable connectors and the feature-rich background, directly identifying the locking mechanism inside an image of e-waste could be not trivial, so more research in this area is needed.

From a manipulation standpoint, the task requires both disengaging specific locking mechanisms and pulling the cable. Using a single robot to perform both operations simultaneously, such as in the disassembly of snap-fit connectors, appears impractical. A more effective strategy may involve a multi-robot system, where one robot disengages the locking mechanism while another pulls the connector. Important directions

of research are the gripper design and manipulation strategy choice. The main challenges are represented by the limited workspace, reachability of target features on the connectors, and avoiding accidental damage to internal e-waste components.

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UTILIZZO DI SMART GLASSES PER L'IMPLEMENTAZIONE DI FUNZIONALITÀ DI SICUREZZA IN APPLICAZIONI ROBOTICHE COLLABORATIVE

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SOMMARIO

Introduzione

La collaborazione uomo-robot (*Human-Robot Collaboration, HRC*) rappresenta una delle principali linee di sviluppo nel contesto della robotica industriale. Questo approccio si caratterizza per un cambio di paradigma rispetto alla robotica tradizionale, poiché prevede uno spazio di lavoro condiviso tra l'operatore umano e il robot, invece di una loro separazione mediante recinzioni di sicurezza o altre attrezzature. Ciò consente di combinare i benefici derivanti dalla presenza degli operatori umani, in termini di flessibilità e capacità di adattamento a condizioni di lavoro variabili, con quelli offerti dai robot, in termini di precisione del processo produttivo e riduzione delle malattie muscoloscheletriche correlate al lavoro ([1]). Si osserva quindi un cambiamento nella direzione di un modello di produzione centrato sull'uomo [2], che comporta tuttavia una serie di nuove sfide per garantire la sicurezza dei lavoratori.

Il problema di assicurare, da un lato, che nessun impatto con il robot possa danneggiare l'operatore e, dall'altro, che l'attività collaborativa sia ergonomicamente adeguata è frequentemente affrontato in letteratura [3]. Tuttavia, [4] evidenzia un gap di ricerca nell'implementazione di funzionalità di sicurezza in risposta a comportamenti scorretti da parte dell'operatore.

Questo lavoro si propone di colmare tale lacuna, introducendo un approccio innovativo per monitorare la concentrazione dell'operatore umano durante l'attività di HRC, migliorando così il livello di sicurezza dell'applicazione. In particolare, l'articolo presenta un algoritmo che, mediante un sistema indossabile di eye-tracking, è in grado di determinare se il lavoratore sta guardando verso l'organo terminale. In caso contrario, possono essere attivate strategie di riduzione del rischio, come l'arresto del robot o la prevenzione dell'attivazione dell'organo terminale.

Materiali e metodi

L'applicazione di HRC considerata in questo studio (Fig. (1)) è un'attività di foratura, in cui l'organo terminale (un trapano pneumatico) di un robot collaborativo Franka Emika Panda

viene posizionato dall'operatore nelle posizioni desiderate, in modalità di manual guidance con controllo di ammettenza [5], per poi simulare l'esecuzione di fori in modo assistito.

L'operatore indossa un paio di smart glasses Neon PupilLabs, dotati di una telecamera anteriore, per monitorare la scena, e di due telecamere posteriori, per rilevare il movimento delle pupille. In questo modo, è possibile verificare che lo sguardo dell'operatore (gaze) sia rivolto nella zona dell'organo terminale.

Per distinguere correttamente l'organo terminale all'interno della scena, infine, sono stati applicati dei marker sul manubrio impugnato dall'operatore, come si osserva in Fig. (1).

Figura 1. Applicazione robotica collaborativa esaminata

Il gaze tracking all'interno della scena inquadrata dalla telecamera anteriore si ottiene direttamente dall'API degli smart glasses: di conseguenza, esso non è stato oggetto di ulteriore studio all'interno di questo lavoro, ma ci si è limitati ad usare il dato fornito dal sistema Neon PupilLabs.

Per quanto riguarda la rilevazione dell'organo terminale, come si è anticipato, si sono invece utilizzati dei marker: in particolare, è stata utilizzata placca rettangolare con quattro marker ArUco opportunamente collocati. A partire da essa, poi, si è ricostruita una regione di interesse (Region of Interest, ROI) all'interno della scena. Tale ROI è stata ottenuta come la proiezione all'interno della scena 2D di un prisma, definito sulla base delle posizioni degli ArUco marker, e contenente l'intero organo terminale (vedi Fig. (2)): si considera di essere in condizioni di sicurezza se, quando l'organo terminale viene attivato, il gaze dell'operatore si trova all'interno della ROI.

Figura 2. Vista CAD dell'organo terminale e del prisma utilizzato per la ROI

Per identificare i marker nella scena si utilizza in prima istanza la libreria ArUco [6]; può tuttavia capitare che l'impiego di tale libreria non abbia successo a causa di movimenti rapidi dell'operatore o di ombreggiature che rendono l'immagine sfuocata. In tal caso, si ricorre al metodo del flusso ottico, secondo l'implementazione di Lucas-Kanade [7], che stima la posizione di un punto all'interno di un'immagine a partire dalla sua posizione nel frame precedente.

In seguito, si utilizza il metodo proposto da Muñoz [8] per stabilire la posizione dei marker ArUco nel sistema di riferimento 3D della telecamera a partire dalla loro posizione nella scena 2D. Una volta noti i quattro punti dei marker nella scena 3D si possono ricostruire le posizioni 3D dei vertici del prisma in Fig. (2), e infine proiettarle nella scena 2D per ottenere la ROI.

Risultati sperimentali

Le prove sperimentali effettuate hanno mostrato che l'algoritmo illustrato riesce a identificare correttamente la ROI nella maggior parte dei frame registrati. In particolare, l'operazione collaborativa descritta in precedenza è stata eseguita da tre diversi operatori con diverse velocità di esecuzione.

Fig. (3) mostra che, quando i movimenti sono stati eseguiti con movimenti lenti, l'identificazione dei marker è quasi sempre stata effettuata con successo con la libreria ArUco. Fig. (4), invece, mostra che, quando i movimenti sono stati eseguiti più rapidamente, l'identificazione è avvenuta nel 20/30% dei frame con il metodo del flusso ottico, e di conseguenza con una precisione inferiore, mentre circa nel 15% dei frame l'identificazione non ha avuto successo. Fig. (5), infine, mostra a titolo esemplificativo un frame: si evidenzia l'area delimitata dai marker identificata dall'algoritmo (linee blu), la ROI (linee rosse) e il punto del gaze (punto verde). Tramite l'algoritmo si può quindi implementare una funzionalità di sicurezza che rileva una situazione di pericolo se il gaze dell'operatore resta al di fuori della ROI oltre un certo tempo limite continuativo.

Figura 3. Risultati dell'identificazione della regione dei marker ArUco con test lenti

Figura 4. Risultati dell'identificazione della regione dei marker ArUco con test veloci

Figura 5. Esempio di un frame in cui il gaze (punto verde) si trova all'interno della ROI (linee rosse) identificata a partire dall'area dei marker (linee blu)

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ANALISI CINETOSTATICA E CINEMATICA DI UN MECCANISMO A VITE PER MOVIMENTAZIONE DI PRECISIONE

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SOMMARIO

Introduzione

I meccanismi a vite sono ampiamente utilizzati quando è necessario realizzare un vincolo di coppia elicoidale con ingombro ridotto e rapporti di riduzione medio-bassi.

Il sistema in studio è un meccanismo a vite di dimensioni minute, il cui scopo è la conversione del moto rotatorio di un motore elettrico in un moto di traslazione di una lente obiettivo con precisione ed accuratezza elevate; queste prestazioni, tuttavia, non sono sempre garantite per la presenza di errori di run-out della vite, i quali portano la lente a spostarsi assialmente e pertanto ad uscire dalla condizione di messa a fuoco. Al fine di disaccoppiare gli spostamenti radiali dovuti al run-out della vite e lo spostamento assiale della lente, nel sistema è presente un giunto di Oldham tra la madrevite e il supporto lente il quale permette alla madrevite di traslare radialmente anziché assialmente. Nel giunto, tuttavia, è presente attrito tra gli elementi che lo compongono e che si oppone al disaccoppiamento completo.

Il meccanismo a vite è ben noto in letteratura e ampiamente studiato, come riportato nei riferimenti [1] e [2], tuttavia questi non approfondiscono lo studio alle condizioni di errori di run-out. Nel presente lavoro si vuole descrivere l'attività di modellazione cinetostatica di un meccanismo a vite in presenza di run-out della vite e l'effetto dell'attrito nel giunto di Oldham nel disaccoppiamento degli spostamenti.

Descrizione del modello

Per la creazione del modello cinetostatico del meccanismo a vite si è scomposto il problema nel caso cinematico e nel caso statico, riportato in Fig. 1a e rappresentante le azioni scambiate tra una porzione svolta di filetto di vite e madrevite; mentre per lo studio dell'effetto dell'attrito radiale nel giunto di Oldham si è fatto uso dello schema riportato in Fig. 1b.

Figura 1 – a) forze scambiate nell'accoppiamento vie-madrevite nel caso statico, b) equilibrio radiale nel piano del giunto di Oldham

Unendo i modelli matematici ricavati dal caso cinematico e dal caso statico del meccanismo a vite, si ottiene il modello cinematico riportato in Eq. (1). In Eq. (2), invece, è riportata l'espressione dell'attrito radiale all'interno del giunto di Oldham.

$$\begin{cases} F_a = F_{ne} \cos \theta \cos \gamma_m + F_{ne} \mu_{din}^{v-m} u_a \\ T = (\mp F_{ne} \cos \theta \sin \gamma_m + F_{ne} \mu_{din}^{v-m} u_t) R_m \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$F_r = F_{ne} \sin \theta + F_{ne} \mu_{din}^{v-m} u_r$$

$$F_{att,R}^{Oldham} = F_A \max_{\varphi \in [0, \frac{\pi}{2}]} \left[\left(\mu_{st}^{m-cr} \cos \varphi + \mu_{st}^{cr-c} \sin \varphi \right) + \left(\frac{\mp \cos \theta \sin \gamma_m + \mu_{din}^{v-m} u_t R_m}{\cos \theta \cos \gamma_m + \mu_{din}^{v-m} u_a} \frac{R_m}{R_c} + \frac{2F_{molla}^{Oldham}}{F_A} \right) \mu_{st}^{v-cr} (\cos \varphi + \sin \varphi) \right] \quad (2)$$

La forza radiale F_r , imposta dalla vite alla madrevite per la presenza di run-out, produce uno spostamento radiale della madrevite stessa nel giunto di Oldham. Affinché lo spostamento radiale della vite e lo spostamento assiale della madrevite siano disaccoppiati, la madrevite deve essere libera di traslare radialmente nel giunto di Oldham; questo movimento, tuttavia, è contrastato dall'attrito e pertanto mai completamente libero.

Si ritiene che la madrevite abbia spostamento assiale trascurabile a seguito di run-out, ovvero trasla radialmente, se la forza d'attrito radiale nel giunto di Oldham è di molto inferiore alla forza radiale trasmessa dalla vite alla madrevite per effetto del run-out, come riportato in Eq. (3).

$$\frac{F_r}{F_{att,R}^{Oldham}} \gg 1 \quad (3)$$

Risultati

Grazie ai modelli trovati è possibile studiare l'effetto dell'angolo d'elica γ_m e dell'angolo di inclinazione del filetto θ nel rapporto tra le forze radiali in Eq. (3), a pari dimensioni geometriche, condizioni d'attrito ed entità di run-out, come riportato in Fig. 2a ($R_{out} = 50 \mu m$), oppure è possibile studiare l'effetto dei coefficienti di attrito statico μ_{st} nel giunto

di Oldham e dinamico μ_{din} tra vite e madrevite nel rapporto in Eq. (3) a pari geometria ed entità di run-out, come riportato in Fig. 2b ($R_{out} = 50 \mu m$).

Figura 2 - a) effetto degli angoli della geometria, b) effetto dei coefficienti d'attrito

Conclusioni e Sviluppi futuri

Grazie ai modelli creati è possibile individuare la geometria ed i materiali ottimali per la realizzazione del meccanismo a vite, quali acciaio e bronzo, e del giunto di Oldham, come il teflon.

Come sviluppi futuri si vuole creare un modello dinamico capace di quantificare le entità degli spostamenti in direzione assiale della madrevite a seguito di uno spostamento radiale della vite, pertanto capace di valutare le performance nella fase di messa a fuoco della lente.

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ANGOLO DI RIBALTAMENTO DI UN TRATTORE AGRICOLA: CALCOLO A NORMA E POSSIBILI AFFINAMENTI

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SOMMARIO

Introduzione

La definizione di angolo di ribaltamento di un trattore agricolo a ruote fa riferimento alla situazione schematica di un trattore in lento movimento su un piano inclinato lungo una generica traiettoria. Al variare dell'angolo tra l'asse longitudinale del trattore e le isoipse rettilinee del piano (angolo β in Fig. 1), variano le reazioni del suolo sulle ruote. Se le intensità delle reazioni sono diverse da zero per tutti gli angoli β salvo uno o due di essi, per i quali la reazione su una delle ruote posteriori si annulla, allora l'angolo d'inclinazione α del piano inclinato è l'angolo (statico) di ribaltamento del trattore.

La norma [1] indica il metodo per il calcolo dell'angolo di ribaltamento di un trattore agricolo ma non menziona i presupposti su cui si basa il metodo.

La letteratura tecnica [2] propone un metodo diverso per determinare l'angolo di ribaltamento: nelle condizioni di ribaltamento incipiente le reazioni del suolo sulle tre ruote di appoggio sono assunte verticali, il che implica che l'impegno di aderenza - cioè il rapporto tra le componenti tangenziale e normale della reazione a terra - sia lo stesso per le tre ruote. Tuttavia l'angolo di ribaltamento è determinato in [2] in modo approssimato, prendendo in esame solo un numero finito di orientamenti del trattore sul piano inclinato, con l'obiettivo di selezionare quello per il quale è minimo l'angolo tra la direzione verticale e la normale al piano inclinato.

In [1] e [2] il trattore è considerato composto dal corpo principale (con annesse ruote posteriori) e dall'assale anteriore (con le relative ruote). L'assale anteriore è rigido e oscillante rispetto al corpo principale grazie a una coppia rotoidale il cui asse è disposto longitudinalmente ed è parallelo al piano di appoggio. Si trascura la massa dell'assale anteriore e delle relative ruote, che sono ipotizzate non sterzate.

La presente memoria si propone di:

- individuare le ipotesi sottese alla procedura di calcolo riportata in [1] e rendere più agevole l'applicazione della procedura;
- velocizzare l'applicazione del metodo di calcolo esposto in [2], eliminando la necessità di calcoli iterativi;
- proporre un nuovo metodo per il calcolo dell'angolo di ribaltamento che tenga conto delle peculiarità della trasmissione di un trattore agricolo a quattro ruote motrici.

Figura 1. Il modello cinematico del trattore

Riformulazione del calcolo a norma

La procedura di calcolo esposta in [1] tacitamente presume che le ruote anteriori siano trascinate. La retta d'azione della reazione del suolo su ciascuna ruota anteriore giace nel piano π ortogonale al piano inclinato e contenente l'asse a-a dell'assale anteriore (v. Fig. 1). Per l'equilibrio alla rotazione dell'assale anteriore attorno all'asse di oscillazione longitudinale, la retta d'azione della risultante delle reazioni del suolo sulle ruote anteriori deve passare per il punto A in cui il piano π interseca il citato asse di oscillazione. In condizione di ribaltamento incipiente il corpo principale del trattore è pertanto in equilibrio sotto l'azione della reazione \mathbf{F}_1 dell'assale anteriore sul corpo principale (applicata in A), della reazione \mathbf{F}_2 del suolo sulla ruota posteriore a valle (applicata in P) e della forza peso \mathbf{F}_3 del corpo principale del trattore (applicata al baricentro G).

Elementari considerazioni di equilibrio consentono di stabilire che le rette d'azione delle forze \mathbf{F}_i ($i=1,2,3$) giacciono nel piano del triangolo ABG. In particolare la retta d'azione di \mathbf{F}_3 interseca il lato AB del triangolo in un punto H la cui posizione può essere espressa come segue

$$\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{P} + \lambda(\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{P}) \quad (1)$$

Il parametro scalare λ che compare nell'Eq. (1) dipende dall'angolo di orientamento β . Scelto un sistema di riferimento con asse z - e versore \mathbf{k} - perpendicolare al piano inclinato, l'angolo tra la verticale e l'asse z è minimo per il seguente valore di λ

$$\lambda = \frac{[(\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{P}) \times (\mathbf{G} - \mathbf{P})] \times (\mathbf{G} - \mathbf{P}) \cdot \mathbf{k}}{[(\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{P}) \times (\mathbf{G} - \mathbf{P})] \times (\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{P}) \cdot \mathbf{k}} \quad (2)$$

Noto λ dall'Eq. (2), e quindi H dall'Eq. (1), si ricava l'angolo α di ribaltamento

$$\alpha = \arccos \frac{(G-H) \cdot \mathbf{k}}{\sqrt{(G-H) \cdot (G-H)}} \quad (3)$$

Benché non esplicitamente dichiarato in [1], il calcolo a norma è calzante solo per trattori a due ruote motrici, i quali non sono tuttavia idonei all'impiego su terreni in pendenza. Resta da verificare se il calcolo sia valido anche per trattori a quattro ruote motrici, gli unici che corrono il rischio di ribaltamento in campo aperto.

La procedura proposta in letteratura

Vengono qui richiamate le ipotesi della procedura di calcolo descritta in [2] e integrate con un metodo per la determinazione diretta e precisa dell'angolo di ribaltamento.

Se le reazioni del suolo sulle tre ruote in appoggio sono verticali, la risultante delle reazioni del suolo sulle due ruote anteriori è una forza verticale la cui retta d'azione interseca: i) il piano inclinato in un punto A_0 del segmento A_1A_2 (v. Fig. 1) e ii) l'asse di oscillazione dell'assale anteriore in un punto B.

Si introducono i parametri $u = (A-B) \cdot \mathbf{i}$ e $v = (A_0-C) \cdot \mathbf{j}$ (\mathbf{i} e \mathbf{j} sono i versori degli assi x e y). Esprimendo le posizioni dei punti B e A_0 mediante u e v, e successivamente imponendo che i punti A_0 , B, G e P siano complanari, si giunge all'equazione

$$f(u, v) = 0 \quad (4)$$

che esprime la condizione di ribaltamento incipiente (f è una funzione bilineare in u e v a coefficienti noti). L'angolo di ribaltamento α si determina imponendo che l'angolo tra la forza peso e la normale al piano inclinato sia minimo, il che corrisponde a minimizzare la quantità $g(u, v) = u^2 + v^2$ nel rispetto dell'Eq. (4). Si perviene pertanto alla condizione

$$u \frac{\partial f}{\partial v} - v \frac{\partial f}{\partial u} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Eliminando algebricamente uno dei parametri - u o v - tra le Eq. (4) e (5), si ottiene un'equazione di quarto grado nel parametro residuo. La radice reale di questa equazione a cui corrisponde il valore minore di $g(u, v)$ porge il valore dell'angolo di ribaltamento

$$\alpha = \arctan \frac{\sqrt{u^2 + v^2}}{h} \quad (6)$$

(h è la distanza dal suolo dell'asse di oscillazione dell'assale anteriore).

La procedura esposta presuppone l'insorgenza di componenti di reazione longitudinali sulle ruote anteriori. È quindi applicabile solo a trattori con quattro ruote motrici. In questi trattori il corpo principale reagisce sull'assale anteriore sia attraverso l'accoppiamento rotoidale interposto, sia attraverso l'albero longitudinale che trasmette il moto alle ruote anteriori. Quest'ultima interazione non è menzionata in letteratura e viene sempre trascurata nella stesura delle condizioni di equilibrio.

Tabella 1. Angoli di ribaltamento α (di direzione β , minimi di aderenza φ_a) [°]

Metodo	Trattore I	Trattore II	Trattore III
Rif. [1]	41.08 (68.13, 41.22)	36.86 (66.70, 37.53)	30.34 (64.94, 33.50)
Rif. [2]	40.81 (64.64, 40.81)	36.24 (60.98, 36.24)	29.05 (56.42, 29.05)
Presente memoria	41.01 (69.40, 41.11)	36.76 (70.09, 36.91)	28.02 (44.77, 31.63)

La nuova procedura

La presenza del differenziale anteriore - qui supposto privo di attrito - in un trattore a quattro ruote motrici assicura che le componenti longitudinali delle reazioni del suolo sulle ruote anteriori siano tra loro uguali. Ciò vale non solo nei casi di trazione e rilascio, ma anche in frenata, considerato che i freni sono generalmente presenti solo sulle ruote posteriori ed esplicano la loro azione anche sulle ruote anteriori per il tramite del differenziale anteriore.

Supponendo dunque tra loro uguali le componenti longitudinali delle reazioni del suolo sulle ruote anteriori e ipotizzando che, in una situazione di ribaltamento incipiente, l'impegno di aderenza per ogni ruota sia il medesimo per le tre ruote di appoggio, si perviene a una nuova procedura per la determinazione dell'angolo di ribaltamento, più realistica della precedente, sebbene di meno semplice formulazione.

Se si indica con $(u, v, -1)$ il vettore forza peso del corpo principale del trattore nel sistema di riferimento $Oxyz$ (v. Fig. 1) e si trascura il momento torcente dell'albero longitudinale che trasmette il moto alle ruote anteriori, si ottiene una relazione algebrica di equilibrio analoga all'Eq. (4), anche se più complessa. La minimizzazione dell'angolo tra la verticale e la normale al piano inclinato si impone ancora mediante l'Eq. (5). L'angolo di ribaltamento è ancora dato dall'Eq. (6), ove h deve ora essere assunto unitario.

Risultati numerici

La Tabella 1 riporta gli angoli di ribaltamento ottenibili coi tre metodi esposti per tre trattori - I, II e III - che differiscono per la posizione longitudinale del loro baricentro. Le coordinate (in mm) dei punti di interesse, nel sistema di riferimento $Oxyz$ mostrato in Fig. 1, sono: $P = (0, 755, 0)$, $A = (2220, 0, 450)$, $G_I = (740, 0, 720)$, $G_{II} = (1110, 0, 720)$, $G_{III} = (1480, 0, 720)$. La medesima tabella riporta pure, tra parentesi, l'angolo di orientamento β e l'angolo di aderenza minimo φ_a necessario affinché si abbia ribaltamento invece di strisciamento lungo il piano inclinato (φ_a riguarda la sola ruota posteriore di valle per il primo metodo e, indistintamente, le tre ruote in appoggio per gli altri due metodi).

Si conclude che il metodo di calcolo a norma è generalmente accettabile anche per i trattori a quattro ruote motrici. In questi, se il baricentro è in posizione avanzata, l'angolo di ribaltamento viene leggermente sovrastimato, a scapito della sicurezza.

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Identification of tire characteristics through a modified Fiala model

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ABSTRACT

Motivations

Inferring tire structural properties from flat-track test data offers valuable insights for both industrial and research applications. This non-invasive approach enables the analysis of tire behavior, including competitor products, only using standard force and moment measurements.

The aim of this study is to evaluate a semi-empirical model's ability to reproduce experimental flat-track data, specifically the lateral force F_y and self-aligning moment M_z as functions of vertical load F_z , and to interpret the resulting parameters in terms of tire structure.

The selected model is the CP/SATP model by Dr. Kabe and Dr. Miyashita, which enhances the classical Fiala model by including three deformation mechanisms: tread shear (C_y), in-plane belt bending (EI_z), and sidewall torsion (k_y), along with an auxiliary parameter ξ accounting for the contact patch shift [1].

The adopted methodology consists in formulating and solving an optimization problem to estimate the model parameters, validating the model's accuracy, and performing a sensitivity and robustness analysis. Finally, the relationship between the identified parameters and the tire's structural features is examined, including their variation with vertical load.

Methodology

The CP/SATP model, an extension of the classical Fiala model, describes tire cornering behavior through two characteristics: Cornering Power (CP), defined as

$F_y(\alpha = 1^\circ, F_z)$, and Self-Aligning Torque Power (SATP), defined as $M_z(\alpha = 1^\circ, F_z)$ [1]. It incorporates three deformation mechanisms: tread shear stiffness C_y , belt bending stiffness EI_z , and sidewall torsion stiffness k_y , plus a compliance parameter ξ representing the backward shift of the contact patch.

The tire is modeled as a spring-bedded ring (Fig. (1)), and the governing equations express F_y and M_z as nonlinear functions of slip angle, tire geometry, and the above mentioned four parameters. Although F_z does not appear explicitly, its effect is captured through the contact patch dimensions $w(F_z)$ and $l(F_z)$, derived from experimental data.

Figure 1. Spring bedded ring model [1]

Flat-track test experimental data, provided by Goodyear, include F_y and M_z measurements for different tire types and loading conditions. A two-step optimization routine was implemented in MATLAB to identify the model parameters:

- A Genetic Algorithm for global search [2];
- A local refinement using `lsqnonlin` for accuracy [3].

The objective function minimizes the squared error between model predictions and experimental data, with equal weighting for F_y and M_z . After optimization, the nonlinear system was solved numerically for each test condition, using a quadratic fit for w and l as functions of F_z .

Results and conclusions

As a case-study, the *Sport2* tire at 2.0 bar is considered. The identified parameters and final objective function value are reported in Tab. (1), showing consistency with literature and good fitting accuracy, as shown in Fig. (2).

To assess the physical meaning of the parameters, two tires with different tread compounds (A: harder, B: softer) were compared. As shown in Tab. (2), only the tread stiffness C_y exhibits a variation consistent with expectations, decreasing by approximately 14% from A to B.

A sensitivity study, not reported here, was carried out to assess the influence of each parameter on the model output, highlighting which parameters have the greatest impact on F_y and M_z . Robustness was also verified by checking solution uniqueness: Fig. (3) shows that parameter variations remain small within acceptable error tolerance.

Figure 2. Sport2 @2.0 - Model output

Parameter	Value
$C_y [N/m^3]$	3.21E08
$k_y [N/m^2]$	3.94E05
$EI_z [N * m^2]$	1.41E03
$\xi [m/N]$	1.25E - 05
f_{val}	4.35E - 03

Table 1. Sport2 @2.0 - Identified parameters

Parameter	A	B	Var-%
$C_y [N/m^3]$	2.53E08	2.17E08	-14.1%
$k_y [N/m^2]$	1.20E05	1.08E05	-10.0%
$EI_z [N * m^2]$	2.36E03	2.97E03	+25.8%
$\xi [m/N]$	2.25E - 05	2.39E - 05	+6.2%

Table 2. Parameter comparison - A vs B

Finally, the load-dependency of the identified parameters was investigated (Fig. (4)). The tread stiffness C_y shows a parabolic trend with F_z , with higher values for performance tires (red) compared to all-season ones (orange), as expected.

Figure 4. Load trends of C_y across tire types

Figure 3. Sport2 @2.0 – Best vs tolerable solutions

In summary, while the CP/SATP model fits the experimental data well and provides robust and consistent parameter estimates, these parameters are not yet sufficient to fully describe the structural characteristics of the tire or to distinguish clearly between different structural design features.

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DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF A HUMAN LOWER LIMB MUSCULOSKELETAL MODEL WITH ADVANCED KNEE AND ANKLE MECHANISMS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction

Musculoskeletal models are currently the main tool for investigating in vivo musculotendon and joint contact forces during gait and/or other physical activities. The growing research for comprehensive models aims to improve joint definition. In replacing of lower pairs, parallel mechanisms [1] have been introduced in musculoskeletal models [2] to best mimic the natural knee and ankle kinematics, and to introduce an explicit representation of contact and ligament constraints. The impact of specific ligaments of the knee and the number of degrees of freedom defined for the ankle are to be examined. Implemented using the TLEM2 dataset [3], four models with similar kinematics but different joint constraints are developed and evaluated, pointing out the impact of each characteristic [4]. The main objectives to be computed in order to evaluate the prediction capability of the model are the tibiofemoral contact forces, for which experimental data (i.e., from an instrumented implant) are available [5].

Material & Methods

The human joints are guided by the articular surfaces (e.g., the femur and tibia condyles for the knee) and passive structures (i.e., the ligaments), and are driven by the muscles. The definition of equivalent mechanisms originates from the identification and modelling of those elements. In the knee, a bundle of fibers in the main ligaments remain almost isometric during motion, while condylar contacts are generally preserved. Thus, a tibiofemoral equivalent mechanism, featuring one degree of freedom (DoF), can be defined as two rigid bodies (the tibia and femur), interconnected by three rigid binary links (representing the three isometric fibers) and by two pairs of surfaces in mutual contact at one point (representing the articular surfaces), as shown in Fig. (1). The patellofemoral joint is modelled as a hinge plus the patellar tendon ligament, reproducing the movement of the patella around the femur articular surface [6]. The ankle is a complex joint involving three segments: tibia, talus and calcaneus. An equivalent mechanism featuring one DoF can be defined using three links converging in

Figure 1. The two versions of the right knee parallel mechanism, featuring different ligaments set (posterior view)

Figure 2. The two versions of the right ankle parallel mechanism, featuring different DoFs

a point and equivalent to a spherical pair coupling the tibia and talus, together with two links (i.e., the TiCaL and CaFiL) coupling the tibia and calcaneus [7]. An extra DoF, which simulates the subtalar kinematics, can be introduced using only two links between the tibia and talus, defined to be kinematically equivalent to a spherical pair between the tibia and talus and a hinge on the subtalar joint [8], as shown in Fig. (2).

These parallel mechanisms were synthesized using the TLEM2 dataset [3], which features a comprehensive representation of bones, cartilage, muscles and ligaments. Natural kinematics was not provided; thus, it was obtained as the envelopes of bone positions and orientations that maximize the joint congruences [9]. The geometric parameters of the mechanisms were optimized to best fit the kinematics while maintaining the articular contacts and ligaments isometry. Two mechanisms for the knee and two for the ankle were synthesized, their combination giving the four model versions. The first knee mechanism includes two sphere-on-plane contacts and three ligaments (i.e., PCL, MCL, and LCL) for the tibiofemoral joint plus the patellofemoral joint. The missing ACL complies with total knee arthroplasty, as in the data used for validation [5]. The second knee mechanism embeds the ACL, MCL and PCL, as in the standard definition of knee parallel mechanism [1]. The two versions of the ankle mechanisms with one or two DoFs are as previously described.

The lower limb model [3] comprises five segments (i.e., pelvis, thigh, patella, shank and foot), four joints (i.e., spherical for the hip; parallel mechanisms for the ankle and knee) and 163 muscle lines of action. The model is driven by virtual markers, and during the inverse kinematics step the sum of their squared distances with the measured skin markers is minimized:

$$\min_Q f = \frac{1}{2}(\boldsymbol{\phi}^m)^T \mathbf{W} \boldsymbol{\phi}^m \text{ subj. to } \begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\phi}^k = \mathbf{0} \\ \boldsymbol{\phi}^r = \mathbf{0} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

with $\boldsymbol{\phi}^m$ representing the differences between measured and model-derived skin marker trajectories, $\boldsymbol{\phi}^r$ the vector of rigid body constraints and $\boldsymbol{\phi}^k$ the vector of kinematic constraints. \mathbf{W} is a diagonal matrix composed of the weights associated with each marker.

All the constraints are represented explicitly, so that the individual forces at the contacts and ligaments are considered and computed during the inverse dynamics (or static optimization) step, that simultaneously minimizes the sum of squared musculotendon, joint contact and ligament forces [2]. They were restricted to a range of minimum and maximum values, the former being 0 to prevent ligaments and muscles from pushing:

$$\min_{\begin{pmatrix} f \\ \lambda_1 \end{pmatrix}} J = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} f \\ \lambda_1 \end{pmatrix}^T \mathbf{W} \begin{pmatrix} f \\ \lambda_1 \end{pmatrix} \text{ subj. to } \begin{cases} \mathbf{Z}_{K_2^T} [\mathbf{L} - \mathbf{K}_1^T] \begin{bmatrix} f \\ \lambda_1 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{Z}_{K_2^T} (\mathbf{G}\ddot{\mathbf{Q}} - \mathbf{R} - \mathbf{P}) \\ \begin{pmatrix} f_{min} \\ \lambda_{1min} \end{pmatrix} \leq \begin{pmatrix} f \\ \lambda_1 \end{pmatrix} \leq \begin{pmatrix} f_{max} \\ \lambda_{1max} \end{pmatrix} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

with J the objective function, \mathbf{W} the weights associated with the unknowns, f the musculotendon forces and λ_1 a subset of Lagrange multipliers that includes ligament and contact forces; \mathbf{G} is the matrix of generalized masses multiplied by the vector of segment's accelerations ($\ddot{\mathbf{Q}}$); \mathbf{R} is the vector of generalized ground reaction forces, \mathbf{P} the vector of generalized weights, \mathbf{L} the matrix of generalized muscular lever arms; $\mathbf{Z}_{K_2^T}$ is the orthonormal basis of the null space of the Jacobian of constraints that are not intended to be computed (K_2^T) while K_1^T is the Jacobian of the constraints to be computed.

Results

Gait trials (n=3 or n=4) of four subjects from the ‘‘Grand Knee Challenge’’ [5] were analyzed with each model version. Marker trajectories were well replicated in all cases; the models with the knee mechanism featuring the PCL, MCL, LCL estimates slightly better the forces, due to a closer similarity to the patient’s joint, as shown in Fig. (3).

To assess the model’s predicting capability, the root mean square (RMS) errors between

Figure 3. Measured and computed tibiofemoral contact and ligament forces from the model having knee mechanism with PCL,MCL,LCL and the 2-Dof ankle mechanism (subject SC)

Table 1. Ranges of RMS errors between measured and computed tibiofemoral contact forces with the four models on the four subjects (in BW)

	SC	PS	JW	DM
Medial	0.26-0.29	0.19-0.23	0.32-0.36	0.27-0.33
Lateral	0.19-0.24	0.24-0.29	0.22-0.33	0.40-0.41

the computed and measured forces have been collected for each patient with each model version and reported in Tab. (1). All the results are expressed in body weight (BW).

Discussion

The development of models with an explicit representation of joint constraints makes it possible to directly calculate and interpret the joint forces comprehensively. All the four proposed versions predict contact forces without personalization, while ligament forces are physiological (i.e., almost unloaded). These models give further information on musculotendon forces, and on hip and ankle joint contacts. The model can be adapted to the outcomes that need to be investigated (e.g., healthy or prosthetic knee).

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BEYOND THE LIMITS OF MINIMIZATION OF MUSCLE ACTIVATION IN JOINT MECHANICS

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Keywords: *Musculoskeletal modelling, knee compliance, joint reaction loads, muscle activation, static optimisation*

ABSTRACT

Introduction

There is an increasing interest in combining musculoskeletal models (MSKM) with advanced, deformable articular models, to investigate articular mechanics [1,2]. The common approach in this case is to use the standard MSKM pipeline to estimate joint reaction, and use these forces and moments as an input to deformable articular models. Typically, in MSKM the joints are considered as rigid and thus capable of fully restrain the secondary degrees of freedom (DoFs). This assumption, together with the chosen static optimisation strategy, determines how joint reactions are computed: in general, muscles do not equilibrate secondary DoFs, assigning this role to joint constraints.

This widely adopted approach has limitations: the number of unrestrained DoF is questioned, with recent investigations suggesting that the knee should be modelled as a 2-DoF joint, with both the flexion/extension and the internal/external rotation balanced by the action of muscles. Also, muscle forces are computed under an inverse dynamic approach, in which the skeletal dynamics is directly reconstructed from skin-mounted markers. In this conditions, the load-induced joint deformation alters the skeletal dynamics, making the final calculation recursive. This loop is however in general not implemented, introducing inconsistency between pre- and post-deformation dynamics.

In this work, we quantify the impact of both these limitations, comparing the joint deformation induced by muscle against experimental quantification of knee kinematics during gait from biplanar fluoroscopy [4], both for a 1-DoF and a 2-DoF knee model, as well as quantifying the impact of making the computation of joint deformation recursive.

Methods

A cohort of 6 healthy subjects (Height: 1.72±0.06 m; Age: 22±3 years) was enrolled. The acquisition took place at the Department of Information Engineering (Padova, Italy). Several gait trials (numerosity: 4±1) were acquired through an 8-camera optoelectronic system

(Vicon, 200 Hz) and 2 force platforms (Bertec, 960 Hz) for ground reaction forces. The IORGait [5] protocol was applied. A general gait2392 MSKM was scaled to each subject. The model's 1-DoF knee secondary kinematics was modified introducing tibiofemoral flexion-dependent splines for each component. A second model was defined in the same way, unlocking the internal-external rotation as the second degree of freedom of the knee. The spline functions were obtained from an experimentally defined map of knee compliance [6], where load-induced deformations are represented as a displacement from the knee's natural motion. The compliance map was built based on 6 specimens characterised through a custom loading rig [7]. A standard MSKM analysis pipeline was executed, and knee joint reaction loads were computed. The tibiofemoral load-dependent spatial kinematics were then calculated in MATLAB, using the knee compliance map and the obtained joint reaction loads. The so obtained deformed kinematics were then compared to kinematic data from the literature, acquired with a mobile biplane X-ray imaging system [4]. After this first comparison, a recursive procedure was introduced in the calculations. This was done by moving the above-explained pipeline inside a loop and progressively updating the model towards the predicted kinematics. At every iteration the overall kinematics is fitted to the experimentally derived marker trajectory information by executing the Inverse Kinematics step of the analysis. The loop ends when the convergence criterion is reached. This criterion is the stabilisation of both the deformation and the joint reaction loads for subsequent iterations (i.e. differences in these terms between the current and the previous iterations can be considered negligible). If needed, a rigidity constant is applied to the deformation to ensure the convergence.

Results

Figure 1 shows the External-Internal rotation of the tibia with respect to the femur for all four cases, against the experimental motion (grey curve).

The 1-DoF-load-dependent model, with no recursive strategy, produces non-physiological results (pink curve), as can be observed in graph 1-A. The introduction of the recursive procedure with the 1-DoF model shows better results (purple curve), but it has required to double joint stiffness ($K = 2$) to reach numerical convergence, as can be observed in graph 1-B. The 2DoF-load-dependent model with no recursive strategy produces better results (light green curve) with respect to the corresponding model with 1-DoF knee, as can be observed in graph 1-C. The introduction of the recursive procedure with the 2DoF model reached convergence with a unitary rigidity constant ($K = 1$). Although the final similarity to the experimental data is slightly lower with respect to the previous case, as can be observed in graph 1-D, the shape of the natural external rotation of the knee is better replicated.

Discussion

Under the rigidity assumption, the 1-DoF load-dependent kinematics determined based on the joint reactions computed by MSKM is incompatible with experimental observations. On the contrary, the 2-DoF load-dependent kinematics is closer to the experimental observations. The introduction of the recursive strategy enlighten additional inconsistencies in the current MSKM approach: the 1-DoF model requires artificially doubling the joint stiffness to reach convergence, while the 2-DoF model produces slightly worse results with respect to the rigid case, although the physiological pattern of motion is replicated.

These observations suggest that alternative strategies are needed to solve the muscle prediction, for instance, considering joint loads in static optimisation [8]. In this direction, preliminary observations confirmed that the knee natural or unloaded motion follows quite well the experimental observation, suggesting that muscles also tend to stabilise the knee, minimising joint reaction and the deviation from this path. The introduction of this new muscle control strategies shown to produce better agreement between muscle-induced joint deformation and experimental observations [9,10]. Future work will combine this new strategy with a recursive calculation, eventually also including an explicit representation of the articular constraints by means of the introduction of parallel mechanisms representing the knee.

Figures and Tables

Figure 1. External-Internal Rotation of the tibia with respect to the femur for the four cases. The legend of the depicted curves is on the right.

Table 1. Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between experimental and rigid (E-R), experimental and deformable (E-D), experimental and deformable with recursive strategy (E-L) knee kinematics, for both 1-DoF and 2-DoF knee models, for Flexion-Extension, Abduction-Adduction, Internal-External rotation angles. Asterisk detects the case that required $K = 2$ rigidity constant to converge.

	<i>FE</i>	<i>AA</i>	<i>IE</i>
<i>1-DoF</i>			
E-R	12.3	0.9	2.6
E-D	11.4	4.3	8.5
*E-L	11.4	1.9	3.4
<i>2-DoF</i>			
E-D	11.6	4.1	6.7
E-L	11.4	3.5	9.2

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VERIFICA DELLA RESISTENZA A PITTING, FLESSIONE E GRIPPAGGIO A CALDO DI PARTICOLARI RUOTE DENTATE CILINDRICHE A DENTI ELICOIDALI

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Keywords: rapporto di condotta trasversale, rigidezza, pitting, flessione, grippaggio

SOMMARIO

Introduzione

In questo studio è stato determinato un metodo per il calcolo della capacità di carico di ruote dentate cilindriche a denti elicoidali aventi rapporto di condotta trasversale ε_α minore di uno.

Il punto di partenza di tale studio è stato il brevetto intitolato “Tooth profile for rotors of positive displacement external gear pumps” realizzato dall’azienda Marzocchi Pompe S.p.A. di Casalecchio di Reno (Bologna) [1].

In questo brevetto viene riportata la definizione analitica di un profilo innovativo dei denti di ruote dentate cilindriche a denti elicoidali per pompe volumetriche a ingranaggi esterni (il volume di olio compreso tra gli spazi dei denti delle due ruote dentate in presa e la scatola esterna viene trasferito dall’ingresso all’uscita del condotto di alimentazione).

I lettori interessati ad approfondire le conoscenze sulla geometria dei denti di ruote dentate cilindriche a denti diritti ed elicoidali possono consultare i testi di Dudley [2], Niemann [3], Henriot [4] e Litvin [5], che presentano una trattazione dettagliata della teoria, del calcolo e del disegno degli ingranaggi, con particolare riferimento a ruote dentate e rotismi.

I risultati di prove sperimentali riportati in questo brevetto dimostrano che il profilo proposto permette di ottenere pompe caratterizzate da ridotta rumorosità, ridotte vibrazioni e oscillazioni di pressione, ridotta usura superficiale ed elevata efficienza, in condizioni operative (pompe ELIKA).

Dal punto di vista geometrico, il profilo studiato è caratterizzato da un rapporto di condotta trasversale ε_α sul fianco del dente compreso nell’intervallo tra 0.4 e 0.45 e da un rapporto di condotta elicoidale ε_β tra i denti elicoidali in presa compreso nell’intervallo tra 0.6 e 0.85.

Dal momento che il rapporto di condotta totale ε_γ , definito come la somma del rapporto di condotta trasversale ε_α e del rapporto di condotta elicoidale ε_β , è maggiore di 1, allora il profilo proposto in questo brevetto garantisce la continuità della trasmissione del moto tra le due ruote dentate in presa.

Dall'altra parte, la normativa attuale relativa alla verifica della resistenza a pitting e a flessione delle ruote dentate cilindriche a denti elicoidali disponibile in letteratura (ISO 6336 del 2006, vedi riferimenti [6–8]) non prevede il caso di un rapporto di condotta trasversale ε_α minore di uno (la normativa esistente considera solo il caso $\varepsilon_\alpha \geq 1$). Nelle versioni precedenti (vedi riferimenti [9–15]) si potevano invece applicare i criteri di verifica della resistenza di ruote dentate cilindriche a denti elicoidali anche nel caso $\varepsilon_\alpha \leq 1$.

L'obiettivo di questo studio è quello di determinare un metodo per il calcolo della capacità di carico di ruote dentate cilindriche a denti elicoidali caratterizzate da un rapporto di condotta trasversale ε_α minore di 1. In questo modo sarà possibile effettuare la verifica della resistenza a pitting e a flessione anche delle ruote dentate cilindriche a denti elicoidali del brevetto.

Il presente lavoro è organizzato nel seguente modo. All'inizio vengono trattati i concetti preliminari come le forze sui denti, le deformazioni e le correzioni sulle tensioni. In seguito vengono applicati i criteri per la verifica della resistenza superficiale a pitting sul fianco del dente, la verifica della resistenza a rottura a flessione al piede del dente e la verifica di resistenza al grippaggio per ruote dentate cilindriche aventi ε_α minore di uno come il caso del brevetto. Nella stesura delle equazioni sono stati analizzati e confrontati libri di testo specifici sulla verifica di resistenza degli ingranaggi e le normative ISO e DIN a cui gli stessi libri fanno riferimento. Sono stati analizzati in modo particolare i coefficienti correttivi che considerano le condizioni effettive di contatto introducendo il numero medio effettivo di coppie di denti in presa, ovvero ε_α . Infine, nelle conclusioni vengono riassunti i metodi utilizzati e le principali differenze rispetto alla normativa vigente.

Verifica della resistenza a pitting

Come esempio del lavoro svolto, per la verifica della resistenza superficiale a pitting della ruota è necessario conoscere la tensione effettiva di contatto sui fianchi dei denti σ_{HB} , che è espressa in funzione della lunghezza dell'asse istantaneo Z_ε e di ε_α , nella forma:

$$\sigma_{HB} = f(Z_\varepsilon), \quad Z_\varepsilon = f(\varepsilon_\alpha) \quad (1)$$

Figura 1. Andamento della lunghezza dell'asse istantaneo Z_ε al variare del valore del rapporto di condotta trasversale ε_α (il rapporto di condotta elicoidale ε_β è fisso)

Come si osserva dalla Figura 1, per un rapporto di condotta trasversale $\varepsilon_\alpha \geq 1$ e per una lunghezza dell'asse istantaneo $Z_\varepsilon \leq 1$, la tensione effettiva di contatto sui fianchi dei denti σ_{HB} è ridotta perché, essendo presenti più coppie di denti in presa, il carico totale risulta maggiormente distribuito.

Al contrario, per un rapporto di condotta trasversale $\varepsilon_\alpha \leq 1$ e per una lunghezza dell'asse istantaneo $Z_\varepsilon \geq 1$, la tensione effettiva di contatto sui fianchi σ_{HB} è elevata, perché essendo presente mediamente un numero inferiore a uno di coppie di denti in presa, sulle coppie stesse che si trovano a contatto è esercitato un carico più concentrato.

Riferimenti

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STRESS SHIELDING EFFECT IN CYLINDRICAL JOINTS WITH CLEARANCE USING FGM

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Keywords: *functionally graded material, cylindrical joints, advancing contact, clearance, analytical solution.*

ABSTRACT

Analytical solutions are presented for the quasi-conformal contact problem with clearance between a loaded rigid pin and a circular ring made of functionally graded material (FGM), which displays a power-law radial variation of the elastic modulus within the thickness. The stress and displacement fields in the FGM ring are taken from the general solution for plane elastic problems involving FGMs in polar coordinates, analogous to Mitchell’s solution for elastic isotropic materials. The frictionless contact conditions yield a set of dual trigonometric series equations that can be reduced to a linear system of infinite equations, then solved by truncation. Due to the nonlinear nature of the advancing contact problem, an inverse method of solution is employed, namely, the contact stress distribution is derived for a set of contact angle values. The corresponding pin load is then calculated, and a nonlinear pointwise relationship is obtained between the contact angle and the pin load. We show that the contact angle can be increased by properly choosing the inhomogeneity factor of the FGM ring. Consequently, more uniform distributions can be achieved for the contact pressure and the hoop stress, thereby preventing mechanical failure in many fasteners and bolt connections. The present findings can assist mechanical engineers in designing innovative pinned connections and improving their load-bearing capacity by exploiting the FGM capabilities.

Introduction

Contact problems of Functionally Graded Materials (FGMs) structures have recently attracted considerable attention in mechanical engineering. These materials have the potential to replace or supplement the surface-hardening technique or the insertion of a harder collar in some applications. Indeed, their composition and properties change gradually over the volume (typically from surface to core). They may display a gradual transition from a hard to a soft phases, from a metallic to a ceramic phase, or even a combination of both. In the field of bearing design, this approach entails the customization of material properties, including hardness, wear resistance, and toughness, across the entire component rather than merely its surface. The gradual variation of material properties inside the bearing surface leads

to a smooth distribution of the stress and strain fields, which could reduce the risk of surface crack initiation and propagation compared to traditional surface-hardened methods. In this work, we provide the analytical solution to the frictionless contact problem between a rigid circular pin and a circular FGM lug, under clearance-fit conditions (Fig. 1). The Young modulus of the FGM ring is assumed to vary in the radial direction according to a power-law and a constant Poisson ratio is assumed. The stress and displacement fields in the elastic plane and the FGM ring are represented using a Michell-type series, which is taken from the solution provided in [1]. Using the frictionless contact boundary conditions, the problem is reduced to the solution of a set of dual trigonometric series equations. Following the approach developed in [2, 3], a linear system of infinite equations for the unknown coefficients of the Michell-type series representations is obtained and then solved by truncation. Results are then presented for the contact pressure and von Mises equivalent stress, for various loading levels, and geometrical and material parameters.

Figure 1. Pin-lug connection and relation between the contact angle α and the pin load.

Problem formulation

Let r_i and r_o denote the inner and outer radii of the FGM lug, respectively. The elastic shear modulus μ of the lug varies along the radial direction according to the relation $\mu = \mu_0 (r/r_i)^m$, where μ_0 is the shear modulus at the inner surface and m is the grading index. It is assumed that the Poisson coefficient ν of the lug is constant. To perform a fully analytical investigation under plane stress or plane strain conditions, we adopt a simplified geometrical model of the pinned connection, by considering an incomplete FGM ring of angular extent 2β (Fig. 1).

The stress-free conditions at the outer surface of the ring require

$$\sigma_{rr}(r_o, \theta) = \sigma_{r\theta}(r_o, \theta) = 0, \text{ for } 0 \leq |\theta| \leq \beta, \quad (1)$$

and the frictionless contact conditions between the rigid pin and the inner surface of the incomplete ring, at $r = r_i$ require

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{r\theta}(r_i, \theta) &= 0, & \text{for } 0 \leq |\theta| \leq \beta, \\ \sigma_{rr}(r_i, \theta) &= 0, & \text{for } \alpha \leq |\theta| \leq \beta, \\ u_{rr}(r_i, \theta) &= \nu_0 \cos \theta - \delta (1 - \cos \theta), & \text{for } 0 \leq |\theta| \leq \alpha, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where α is the unknown contact half-angle, v_0 denotes a rigid body motion of the pin along the loading direction, and δ is the clearance. Moreover, the constraint at the edges of the incomplete ring, namely at $\theta = \pm\beta$, requires $u_\theta(r, \pm\beta) = \sigma_{r\theta}(r, \pm\beta) = 0$, for $r_i < r < r_o$. The cylindrical components of the stress and displacement fields within the FGM ring are represented using a Michell-type series containing only even terms in θ . They follow from the solution presented in [1] for a power-law radial variation of the elastic modulus, by replacing n with $n\pi/\beta$, for $n = 1, 2, 3 \dots$ to meet the boundary conditions at $\theta = \pm\beta$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\sigma_{rr}}{2\mu} &= \frac{\delta}{r_o} \left[\sum_{i=1}^2 B_{0i} \left(\frac{r}{r_o} \right)^{a_i} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i=1}^4 B_{ni} \left(\frac{r}{r_o} \right)^{b_{ni}} \cos \frac{n\pi\theta}{\beta} \right], \\
\frac{\sigma_{\theta\theta}}{2\mu} &= \frac{\delta}{r_o} \left[\sum_{i=1}^2 B_{0i} (a_i + 1) \left(\frac{r}{r_o} \right)^{a_i} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i=1}^4 B_{ni} \left(\frac{r}{r_o} \right)^{b_{ni}} (b_{ni} + 2) \Delta_{ni} \cos \frac{n\pi\theta}{\beta} \right], \\
\frac{\sigma_{r\theta}}{2\mu} &= \frac{\delta}{r_o} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i=1}^4 B_{ni} \left(\frac{r}{r_o} \right)^{b_{ni}} \frac{n\pi}{\beta} \Delta_{ni} \sin \frac{n\pi\theta}{\beta}, \\
\frac{u_r}{\delta} &= \sum_{i=1}^2 B_{0i} \kappa_i \left(\frac{r}{r_o} \right)^{a_i+1} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i=1}^4 B_{ni} \left(\frac{r}{r_o} \right)^{b_{ni}+1} \frac{\chi_{1ni}}{2(1-\rho^2)} \cos \frac{n\pi\theta}{\beta}, \\
\frac{u_\theta}{\delta} &= \frac{\beta}{2(1-\rho^2)\pi} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i=1}^4 B_{ni} \left(\frac{r}{r_o} \right)^{b_{ni}+1} \frac{\chi_{2ni}}{n} \sin \frac{n\pi\theta}{\beta},
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where $\mu = \mu_0 (r/r_i)^m$ is the elastic shear modulus of the FGM ring. The contact conditions (1) and (2) yield a mixed boundary value problem with a moving boundary, which can be formulated in terms of dual trigonometric series equations. Following the approach developed in [2, 3] a linear system of infinite equations for the unknown coefficients B_{ni} of the Michell-type series representations is obtained and then solved by truncation.

Results

The normalized distributions of the contact pressure with the angular coordinate θ are plotted in Fig. 2 for a lug with aspect ratio $r_i/r_o = 0.5$ and for various contact angles, both for $m = 1$ and $m = -1$. In general, the same pin load causes larger contact angle for negative grading index than for positive ones (Fig. 1). The results show that the Hertzian distribution of the contact pressure is valid only for very low load levels and a small contact zone (black lines). As the load magnitude increases, two pressure bumps take place near the contact endpoints, and the contact pressure becomes almost uniform in the central part of the contact region. The position of the peaks depends on the ring thickness and grading index. It approaches the edges of the contact region for a very thin ring as well as for negative m , whereas it moves toward the center for thicker rings and positive m . The contour plots of the normalized von Mises equivalent stress $\sigma_{eq} r_i/P$ in the right-side region ($0 \leq \theta \leq \beta$) of a lug with $r_i/r_o = 0.5$ are illustrated in Fig. 3 for the same contact angle $\alpha = 0.45 \pi$, for $m = 1, 0$, and -1 . These plots show that the maximum von Mises equivalent stress occurs at about $\theta \approx 73^\circ$ on the inner surface of the lug, independently of the grading index. The equivalent stress on the outer lug surface is much lower than on the inner surface, especially for the negative grading index m . This occurrence suggests that the load-bearing capacity of the pin-lug connection can be

enhanced by realizing a FGM lug with a negative grading index, namely by increasing both the elastic modulus and the strength of the FGM lug near the surface in contact with the loaded pin.

Figure 2. Normalized variations of the contact pressure p with the angular coordinate θ for various contact angles, for $m = 1$ and $m = -1$.

Figure 3. Contour plots of the normalized von Mises equivalent stress $\sigma_{eq} r_i / P$ in the FGM ring with $r_i / r_o = 0$, for $\alpha = 0.45 \pi$, for $m = 1, 0, -1$.

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INTEGRATING DIGITAL TWINS AND DEEP LEARNING FOR PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE OF BONDED INSULATED RAIL JOINTS

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Keywords: *Digital Twin of bonded insulated rail joints, Time-frequency analysis for data processing, Deep Learning for Predictive Maintenance.*

ABSTRACT. Integrating digital twins (DTs) and deep convolutional neural networks (DCNNs) is a significant advance in the smart structural health monitoring (SHM) of rail infrastructure. To this end, we have developed a DT of a bonded insulated rail joint (IRJ) that can effectively simulate its mechanical behaviour when a pair of wheels passes over it. We collected the gap value from DTs, which is a parameter that is strongly correlated with the bolt preload conditions of the joint. This value was converted into image representations using time-frequency analysis, which were then used to train and test the DCNN architecture for fault diagnosis. The high accuracy of the trained networks confirms the importance of this research for the railway sector, whose safe and continuous operation is crucial for the well-being and development of nations.

Introduction

Railway infrastructure plays an indispensable role in modern transportation systems, favouring economic and social growth and sustainable development [1]. Bonded IRJs are designed to handle significant forces and ensure electrical insulation and mechanical continuity between rails. However, they can suffer from loosening bolts, cracks and progressive wear, which can lead to instability. This is difficult to predict using traditional maintenance methods [2]. As rail mobility becomes smarter, PdM which is powered by data-driven models, offers a transformative solution for monitoring, assessing and predicting the condition of IRJs to avoid unexpected failures and reduce costs [3].

DTs, virtual models that simulate the behaviour of railway infrastructure have shown tremendous promise, providing a precise representation of how the components respond to different loads and conditions, enabling engineers to simulate and analyse potential failures in a safer and more reliable environment. However, DTs alone are insufficient for PdM. To realise their full potential, they must be integrated with advanced AI algorithms that can analyse the large, complex datasets they generate to predict the remaining useful life of components, failure locations, and maintenance needs [4]. In [5], the authors successfully presented the integration of DT for a bonded IRJ subject to bolt preload loss and a predictive ML classifier. The DT output parameters, the vertical displacement and longitudinal displacements of adjacent rails, also known as gap values, were used to train a predictive ML model that can distinguish between normal operation and imminent failure of the IRJ.

Considering the promising results achieved in monitoring mechanical components [6] and road pavements [7], this study proposes a PdM model based on time–frequency analysis and DCNNs, trained and tested using time samples related to the gap value of digital IRJs under different bolt preload conditions. The presented method can be summarised as follows. Firstly, the DT of the bonded IRJ is implemented because its output is required to train and test the predictive model. Secondly, the DT time-domain data is converted using time-frequency analysis methods, such as short-time Fourier transform (STFT) and wavelet transform (WT), to obtain the corresponding time-frequency images, i.e. spectrograms and scalograms. Thirdly, these images can be fed into CNNs, i.e. powerful DL architectures capable of automatically classifying new data, thanks to their ability to capture transient features and subtle fault signatures. Finally, the effectiveness of two time-frequency methods, STFT-CNN and WT-CNN, is compared using performance indicators that assess their ability to predict whether new data originates from a safely bolted IRJ or indicates an anomaly.

Material and Methods

Digital Twin Modelling. The main considerations of the new research activity are reported below, by following the DT model implementation techniques for bonded IRJs that have been developed in [5]. We used the commercial software Abaqus/CAE with a simplified geometry that remains faithful to rail type 50 UNI, shown in Fig. 1a. Two 9-metre sections of track are connected by two fishplates and secured by four bolts. We applied preload to each bolt, starting with a value of 75 kN in the safe condition, and then reducing it; we investigated the behaviour of the IRJ at 50 kN and 25 kN for different loosened bolt configurations. Finally, we collected the gap value caused by a pair of wheels of a regional train passing over the joint by inserting the appropriate probes corresponding to the orange dots in Fig. 1b, as this output is related to the structural health condition of the IRJ.

Figure 1. a Cross section of IRJ; b bonded IRJ with orange probes.

DCNN with Time-Frequency Analysis Methods. To evaluate the conditions of bonded IRJs under different bolt preloads, we adapted a DL strategy presented in [6, 7] to the railway system. The process can be summarised in three phases: transforming data from the time domain into images in the time-frequency-energy domain; training CNNs which excel in their ability to analyse image representations of data; and finally testing by detecting and classifying structural health conditions.

Firstly, all the outputs obtained from the DT of bonded IRJ are stored in a dedicated worksheet containing 60 representative simulations for each of the three structural health classes: “safe” for IRJ with all bolts preloaded at 75 kN, “warning” and “risk” for IRJ with a combination of bolt loosened at 50 kN and 25 kN, respectively. Figure 2a shows the gap values for each of the three conditions in the time domain. Then, the DT outputs are converted into spectrograms and scalograms, i.e. images in the time-frequency-energy domain, using

the STFT and WT, respectively. Both types of representation can capture features and subtle fault signatures that conventional signal analysis methods might overlook. Figures 2 b-c show the spectrogram and scalogram of a “safe” IRJ, obtained using MATLAB.

Once the DT output has been converted into images, the dataset is divided into 80% training data and 20% test data for each class. These representations can be used to train DCNN architectures to automatically detect and classify faults. To overcome the requirement for large amounts of training data needed to achieve a high level of predictive capability, we use Transfer Learning (TL). This involves using a DCNN pre-trained on an annotated image dataset, thus avoiding the need for long parameter adjustments and complex fine-tuning regulations. We chose a simple pre-trained model, i.e. GoogLeNet, available in MATLAB, which allowed us to iterate quickly and experiment with different data preprocessing steps and training options. Finally, we evaluated and compared the predictive effectiveness of the STFT-CNN and WT-CNN, based on the classification indicators described in next section.

Figure 2 a Examples of gap value for the 3 structural health classes; b-c spectrogram and scalogram for a “safe” joint.

Results

The performance indicators of the predictive STFT-CNN and WT-CNN, which are explained in detail in [5], are presented in Tab. 1. In short, accuracy indicates the ability to correctly identify structural health classes. Precision reflects the quality of positive predictions, focusing on minimising false positives, while recall measures how well a model identifies all positive instances in a dataset, focusing on minimising false negatives. F1-score combines precision and recall, indicating the correct balance of the model.

Table 1. Testing performance indicators for STFT-CNN and WT-CNN.

Class	STFT-CNN			WT-CNN		
	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score (%)
Safe	100	100	100	80	100	88.9
Warning	100	100	— 100	100	75	85.7
Risk	100	100	100	100	100	100
Accuracy (%)	100			91.7		

The indicators in Tab. 1 show that both trained DCNNs achieved exceptional predictive capabilities, with accuracies of 91.7% for the CW-CNN and 100% for the STFT-CNN, which is claimed to be the most effective method for the considered data. By analysing the WT-

CNN errors, we observe that the gap values of the “safe” and “warning” joints with the external bolt pair loosened are very similar. This confirms that their contribution to the IRJ’s mechanical response is minimal, with only the STFT-CNN distinguishing them correctly. Finally, we can confirm that advanced DL techniques for fault diagnosis can automatically learn complex patterns from data, making them far more effective than traditional techniques.

Conclusion

We observed that DL models, which exploit automatic feature extraction, can distinguish between normal and faulty operating conditions by utilising the responses of a DT simulating the behaviour of a bonded IRJ with time-frequency image analysis, improving diagnostic accuracy and enables real-time PdM. The DT collection of gap value data is closely linked to the condition of the joint, and this data is also simple to measure in a bonded IRJ using classical or modern monitoring techniques. Both trained predictive models presented very high-performance indicators, confirming that investigating and developing these innovative tools is essential for anticipating fault formation and facilitating the coordination of railway infrastructure maintenance activities. This reduces time and costs while ensuring greater continuity and safety of rail services.

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ABOUT EXPERIMENT-BASED FULL-FIELD RECEPTANCES IN AIRBORNE FATIGUE PREDICTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction

What is the effect of an acoustic-pressure field on a flexible vibrating surface? While experiment modal analysis and model updating are the more common activities that can get enhancements from experiment-based full-field receptances, further investigations can achieve strong boosts when the real structure is retained in the simulations, without simplifications of untuned models: pseudo-inverse vibro-acoustics and related fatigue life assessment studies. These works are spin-off activities fostered by the grown seeds put in the *Speckle Interferometry for Industrial Needs* and the *Towards Experimental Full-Field Modal Analysis* projects.

Experiment-based full-field \mathbb{C} receptances

Full-field dynamic testing can nowadays be achieved by means of optical measurements, to estimate experiment-based *receptances* on the whole sensed surface of the specimen under test. *Receptance FRF & Coherence function* maps at specific frequencies and excitation sources can be obtained as in [1, 2], to appreciate the spatial consistency & continuity of the data, with clean shapes, sharp nodal lines on the *Receptances* and excellent *Coherences*. A very brief summary of what was available at TU-Wien follows: a dedicated room with a seismic floor; a mechanical and electronic workshop with technicians at disposal; traditional tools for vibration & modal analysis; but, in particular, there were SLDV, Hi-Speed DIC and ESPI measurement instruments. Accurate studies were needed to understand each technological limit and if a common test for concurrent usage might have been really possible. All this brought to a unique set-up for the comparison of the 3 optical technologies in full-field FRF measurements; great attention was paid on the design of experiments for further research in modal analysis. Looking at the most recent publications, in [1] a gathering of the works of TEFFMA was firstly attempted, while in [2] an extensive description of the whole receptance testing was faced and in [3] the EFFMA was detailed together with model updating attempts. The works in [4] underlined the quality of the datasets in full-field dynamic testing. In [5] a precise comparison was made about new achievements for rotational and strain FRF high resolution maps. To the interested reader, the most detailed test campaign appeared in [2], with further suggestions in [3–5].

Figure 1. Examples of simulated \mathbb{R} pressure fields acting on a flexible plate and its full-field \mathbb{C} receptances, inducing the force in shaker 1, at specific frequencies.

Airborne pseudo-inverse vibro-acoustics

The Rayleigh's integral formulation, fed with the *full-field experiment-based receptances* obtained in the TEFFMA project, was investigated in [6–8] for the numerical approximation of the sound radiation field in the *direct vibro-acoustics*. For the *pseudo-inverse vibro-acoustics*, a specific formulation was developed in [9–13]: Fig.1 shows the simulated acoustic pressure fields, to drive the induced force, as shown in Fig.2.

Spectral methods for fatigue predictions

The experiment-based mapping of the equivalent stresses can be achieved from force spectra and proper constitutive models. Fatigue spectral methods turn this knowledge into components' life distributions, which lead to the assessment of where the material reaches first the critical conditions for a failure, whereas can highlight areas of under utilization. Therefore, a risk grading mapping for potential defects can be formulated (see [14–16]) over the area of inquiry in order to discriminate among safe and dangerous locations. The full-field mappings in fatigue related studies were further developed in [17–19]. Indeed, defect acceptance can be seen dependable upon the mapping of effective strains, due to dynamic loading of the components as they are mounted. By following this experiment-based approach, potential defects in exercise and production might be tolerated in safer locations, under the chosen dynamic task, with great savings in costs and maintenance, as in Fig.3, where the induced airborne force was used as excitation spectrum.

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Figure 2. Examples of pseudo-inverse vibro-acoustic FRF in dof 1092 and shaker 1 in *a*; of identified C airborne force in shaker 1 in *b*.

Figure 3. Examples of von Mises equivalent stress PSD in *a* and frequency-to-failure distribution in *b*, from the induced airborne excitation in shaker 1.

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